

REVISTA NICARAGÜENSE DE BIODIVERSIDAD

N° 82.

Abril 2023

Checklist of the birds of Nicaragua.

Liliana Chavarría - Duriaux

PUBLICACIÓN DEL MUSEO ENTOMOLÓGICO
LEÓN - - - NICARAGUA

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The Revista Nicaragüense de Biodiversidad (ISSN 2413-337X) is a journal created to help a better divulgation of the research in this field in Nicaragua. Two independent specialists referee all published papers.

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Front page picture: Bonaparte's Gull - *Chroicocephalus philadelphia* (photo by Danilo Moreno).

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RESUMEN

Este trabajo presenta una actualización de la Lista Patrón de las Aves de Nicaragua tomando como base las publicaciones anteriores, siendo la última la de 2018. Se enlistan 782 especies incluyendo 19 nuevos registros: *Podiceps nigricollis*, *Paraclaravis mondetoura*, *Laterallus jamaicensis*, *Limosa haemastica*, *Arenaria melanocephala*, *Calidris pugnax*, *Chroicocephalus philadelphia*, *Puffinus lherminieri*, *Nannopterum auritum*, *Plegadis chihi*, *Asio flammeus*, *Tyrannus caudifasciatus*, *Progne sinaloae*, *Mimus polyglottos*, *Turdus rufopalliatus*, *Chondestes grammacus*, *Melospiza lincolni*, *Limnothlypis swainsonii* y *Leiothlypis celata*. La información sobre los nuevos registros fue obtenida revisando los datos de ebird, entrevistando a los observadores y comprobando la documentación de los mismos. Se actualiza la tabla de especies incluyendo el orden taxonómico y los cambios en la nomenclatura; se actualizan las ampliaciones de distribución, de rango altitudinal y de abundancia. La tabla muestra la siguiente información: nombre científico y nombre en español, familias, los hábitats usados por cada especie, el rango altitudinal en que se encuentran, la distribución y abundancia, y el estatus. Es nueva en esta lista la información de vulnerabilidad de acuerdo a la Lista Roja de la UICN.

PALABRAS CLAVES: aves, abundancia, lista patrón, Nicaragua, nuevos registros, rango altitudinal.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7538910

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an update of the Checklist of the Birds of Nicaragua based on previous publications, the latest being that of 2018. It lists 782 species including 19 new records: *Podiceps nigricollis*, *Paraclaravis mondetoura*, *Laterallus jamaicensis*, *Limosa haemastica*, *Arenaria melanocephala*, *Calidris pugnax*, *Chroicocephalus philadelphia*, *Puffinus lherminieri*, *Nannopterum auritum*, *Plegadis chihi*, *Asio flammeus*, *Tyrannus caudifasciatus*, *Progne sinaloae*, *Mimus polyglottos*, *Turdus rufopalliatus*, *Chondestes grammacus*, *Melospiza lincolni*, *Limnothlypis swainsonii* and *Leiothlypis celata*. Information on new records was obtained by reviewing ebird data, interviewing observers and checking observer documentation. The species table is updated including taxonomic order and nomenclatural changes; distribution, altitudinal range extensions and abundance are updated. The table shows the following information: scientific name and English name, families, the habitats used by each species, the altitudinal range in which they are found, the distribution and abundance, and the status. New to this list is the vulnerability information according to the IUCN Red List.

KEY WORDS: birds, abundance, checklist, new records, Nicaragua, altitudinal range.

INTRODUCTION

The first edition of the *Lista Patrón de las Aves de Nicaragua* (Martínez-Sánchez) was published in 2000 by the Cocibolca Foundation, the second by the same author in 2007 by ALAS (*Alianza para las Áreas Silvestres*). In 2010 Howell's Check-list of the birds of Nicaragua as of 1993, completed and edited by Martínez-Sánchez and Tom Will, was published, this was an extremely valuable contribution to the knowledge of the distribution, abundance and habitat use of the birds of Nicaragua. It also lists the expected species that could be found in the country. Subsequently ALAS published in 2014 "A Guide to the Birds of Nicaragua *Una Guía de Aves*", the first guide to the birds of Nicaragua with texts in Spanish and English. The latest published checklist of the country's birds is contained in *Birds of Nicaragua a Field Guide* p. 421 (Chavarría-Duriaux *et al.* 2018).

Taking into account the new records reported since 2018, the range extension of species already recorded, the changes in knowledge about the abundance of the different species, as well as the vulnerability that affects certain species due to the loss of their habitats, and the taxonomic changes published in the annual supplements of AOS (American Ornithological Society) make necessary the publication of this new Checklist of the Birds of Nicaragua updated to 2022.

Scientific and English names are based on the Checklist of North and Middle American Birds updated to supplement 62. 2021.

[<https://checklist.americanornithology.org/taxa/>]

Symbol key to the main table

Vulnerability

The first column on the far right shows the degree of global vulnerability of each species according to the IUCN Red List until 2022. It is important to note that certain species that are listed as LC (Least Concern) are actually vulnerable in Nicaragua or present some type of threat. These species, for the most part, are those that use Caribbean rainforest habitats where land use change is evident.

LC	Least Concern	(734 species)
NT	Near Threatened	(28 species)
VU	Vulnerable	(16 species)
EN	Endangered	(3 species)
CR	Critically Endangered	(1 species)

List of species with some degree of vulnerability (48 species)

CR	Psittacidae	<i>Ara ambiguus</i>	Great Green Macaw
EN	Rallidae	<i>Laterallus jamaicensis</i>	Black Rail
	Procellariidae	<i>Pterodroma hasitata</i>	Black-capped Petrel
	Parulidae	<i>Setophaga chrysoparia</i>	Golden-cheeked Warbler
VU	Tinamidae	<i>Crypturellus boucardi</i>	Slaty-breasted Tinamou
	Cracidae	<i>Penelopina nigra</i>	Highland Guan
	Cracidae	<i>Crax rubra</i>	Great Curassow
	Odontophoridae	<i>Cyrtonyx ocellatus</i>	Ocellated Quail

Cuculidae	<i>Neomorphus geoffroyi</i>	Rufous-vented Ground-Cuckoo
Apodidae	<i>Cypseloides niger</i>	Black Swift
Procellariidae	<i>Procellaria parkinsoni</i>	Parkinson's Petrel
Procellariidae	<i>Ardenna creatopus</i>	Pink-footed Shearwater
Ardeidae	<i>Agamia agami</i>	Agami Heron
Accipitridae	<i>Harpia harpyja</i>	Harpy Eagle
Momotidae	<i>Electron carinatum</i>	Keel-billed Motmot
Psittacidae	<i>Eupsittula canicularis</i>	Orange-fronted Parakeet
Psittacidae	<i>Amazona auropalliata</i>	Yellow-naped Parrot
Cotingidae	<i>Procnias tricarunculatus</i>	Three-wattled Bellbird
Tyrannidae	<i>Aphanotriccus capitalis</i>	Tawny-chested Flycatcher
Hirundinidae	<i>Progne sinaloae</i>	Sinaloa Martin

NT

Cracidae	<i>Penelope purpurascens</i>	Crested Guan
Odontophoridae	<i>Rhynchortyx cinctus</i>	Tawny-faced Quail
Columbidae	<i>Patagioenas leucocephala</i>	White-crowned Pigeon
Caprimulgidae	<i>Antrostomus carolinensis</i>	Chuck-will's-widow
Caprimulgidae	<i>Antrostomus vociferus</i>	Eastern Whip-poor-will
Apodidae	<i>Chaetura cinereiventris</i>	Gray-rumped Swift
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius melodus</i>	Piping Plover
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius nivosus</i>	Snowy Plover
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris canutus</i>	Red Knot
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris subruficollis</i>	Buff-breasted Sandpiper
Scolopacidae	<i>Calidris pusilla</i>	Semipalmated Sandpiper
Laridae	<i>Thalasseus elegans</i>	Elegant Tern
Hydrobatidae	<i>Hydrobates leucorhous</i>	Leach's Storm-Petrel
Procellariidae	<i>Puffinus opisthomelas</i>	Black-vented Shearwater
Ardeidae	<i>Egretta rufescens</i>	Reddish Egret
Accipitridae	<i>Morphnus guianensis</i>	Crested Eagle
Accipitridae	<i>Spizaetus ornatus</i>	Ornate Hawk-Eagle
Accipitridae	<i>Buteogallus solitarius</i>	Solitary Eagle
Trogonidae	<i>Pharomachrus mocinno</i>	Resplendent Quetzal
Ramphastidae	<i>Ramphastos sulfuratus</i>	Keel-billed Toucan

Ramphastidae	<i>Ramphastos ambiguus</i>	Yellow-throated Toucan
Falconidae	<i>Falco deiroleucus</i>	Orange-breasted Falcon
Tyrannidae	<i>Contopus cooperi</i>	Olive-sided Flycatcher
Vireonidae	<i>Vireo bellii</i>	Bell's Vireo
Icteridae	<i>Sturnella magna</i>	Eastern Meadowlark
Parulidae	<i>Vermivora chrysoptera</i>	Golden-winged Warbler
Parulidae	<i>Setophaga cerulea</i>	Cerulean Warbler
Thraupidae	<i>Lanio leucothorax</i>	White-throated Shrike-Tanager

Status

Refers to the time or periods of time that the species can be found in the country. Due to the dynamism of birds, not all of them can be found throughout the year. We are talking about migrations from the northern hemisphere to the south and vice versa, without taking into account the altitudinal or feeding movements of resident and breeding species.

Some species have more than one category. E.g. M, R: this species would have both migratory and resident populations. Another example: MP, R: there are migratory populations passing through as well as resident.

- R Residents. Species that breed and are found all year round in Nicaragua.
- M Northern migrants. They breed in the northern hemisphere and spend their boreal winter season in Nicaragua, Central America and South America (boreal winter residents). They spend 6 to 8 months in the country between August and May.
- PM Passage migrant. Species that pass through Nicaragua on their fall migration to their southernmost wintering grounds (August to November) and on their spring migration to their northern breeding grounds (March to May). They do not maintain resident wintering populations. The months of passage vary according to species.
- S Breeding migrant. They breed in Nicaragua (between February and August). They migrate to South America where they spend the austral summer.
- P/S Southern migrants passing through Nicaragua.
- P Pelagic. Species that breed on distant islands and whose seasonality pattern does not show a defined pattern.
- V Vagrant . One or few records out of range.

Distribution and abundance (third column from right to left).

This column contains a lot of information. The geographical region where a species is found is given in capital letters; it always starts with Pacific (P) and ends with Caribbean (Cb). Occasionally, next to the letter indicating the geographic region, indicators of cardinal points are presented in lower case, e.g. Cb so, indicating that it is in the Caribbean, but in the southwest zone. Next to the right, and between parentheses appear the symbols of abundance.

? insufficient data

Geographical regions.

P Pacific

L Lacustrine depression (great lakes)

C Central. Refers to the North Central Highlands

Cb Caribbean

Cardinal points (modifiers)

n north

s south

e east

w west

ne northeast

nw northwest

se southeast

sw southwest

Other modifiers

i islands

v volcanoes

Abundance

- a Abundant. Can be seen in the field almost every day, sometimes in large numbers.
- c Common. Recorded on 50% of the days. It is frequently encountered.
- u Uncommon. Observed less than 50% of the days. Infrequent encounters.
- r Rare. Observed in the field on less than 10% of days.
- vr Very rare. There are few records. An experienced observer may not find the species for several years.
- l Found only in specific locations. Can be combined with the other abundance terms: e.g., locally rare or locally common.
- Ac Accidental. Extremely few records.
- ext? Extirpated or extinct.
- s Seasonal. For birds that make altitudinal or feeding migrations.

Altitudinal range (fourth column from left to right).

Indicates the altitudinal range (expressed in meters) in which the species is commonly found, e.g. 0 - 100; sometimes it is not a range, but an altitude followed by a + sign, e.g. 1000 +, meaning "from 1000 meters and above".

Note that in some species there are two ranges separated by semicolons (;) e.g. Pacific and Central. Ex: 0-50; 1000+. As the information always starts from the west towards the east (Pacific to Caribbean), this indicates that in the Pacific it is found from 0 to 50 m, and in the Center above 1000 m (according to the information that appears in the column of distribution and abundance).

Habitat (fifth column from right to left).

- F Forest (all types)
- DF Dry forest
- WF Wet forest
- CF Cloud forest
- FE Forest edge
- PF Pine and oak forest or pine forest

- SP Pine savannah
- SF Secondary forest, secondary growth, coffee plantations, cocoa plantations
- EX Thorn forest with xerophytic vegetation
- R Riparian, forested river edge
- S Scrub
- FG Flooded grasslands
- O Open areas, grasslands, agricultural areas
- P Pelagic zone, offshore ocean waters
- W Inland and coastal wetlands
- Bm Bamboo
- Mg Mangroves
- U Urban

New records

- N New record. Column located to the right of the scientific names' column.

Checklist of the birds of Nicaragua.

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	IUCN
	Tinamidae	Tinamous					
1	<i>Tinamus major</i>	Great Tinamou	WF, PS, CF	0-1400	C (r,l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
2	<i>Crypturellus soui</i>	Little Tinamou	WF, PS, CF	0-1400	C (r,l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
3	<i>Crypturellus cinnamomeus</i>	Thicket Tinamou	DF, CF	0-1400	P (c), C (c,l)	R	LC
4	<i>Crypturellus boucardi</i>	Slaty-breasted Tinamou	CF	0-1400	C (r,l), Cb (c, l)	R	VU
	Anatidae	Ducks					
5	<i>Dendrocygna autumnalis</i>	Black-bellied Whistling-Duck	W	0-1000	P (a), C (a), Cb(a)	R	LC
6	<i>Dendrocygna bicolor</i>	Fulvous Whistling-Duck	W	0-1000	P (c), C (c,l), Cb (c,l)	R	LC
7	<i>Cairina moschata</i>	Muscovy Duck	W	0-1000	P (u, l), C (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
8	<i>Spatula discors</i>	Blue-winged Teal	W	0-1300	P (a), C (a), Cb(a)	M	LC
9	<i>Spatula cyanoptera</i>	Cinnamon Teal	W	0-150	P (r), Cb (ac)	M	LC
10	<i>Spatula clypeata</i>	Northern Shoveler	W	0-1000	P (c), C (c,l), Cb (u,l)	M	LC
11	<i>Mareca americana</i>	American Wigeon	W	0-1200	P (u-c), C (u), Cb (u)	M	LC
12	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Mallard	W	0-1000	P (ac), C (ac)	V	LC
13	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Northern Pintail	W	0-1000	P (u-c), C (u-c), Cb (u,l)	M	LC
14	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Green-winged Teal	W	0-450	P (r), C sw (u,l) Cb (u,l, ac)	M	LC
15	<i>Aythya valisineria</i>	Canvasback	W	0-100	Lne (ac)	V	LC
16	<i>Aythya americana</i>	Redhead	W	0-500	P (r,l)	M	LC
17	<i>Aythya collaris</i>	Ring-necked Duck	W	0-1200	P (u,l), C (u,l), Cb (u,l)	M	LC
18	<i>Aythya marila</i>	Greater Scaup	W	0-1000	P (ac), C (ac), Cb (ac)	M	LC
19	<i>Aythya affinis</i>	Lesser Scaup	W	0-1200	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UCN
20	<i>Nomonyx dominicus</i>	Masked Duck	W	0-1200	P (u), C (u), CS (r)	R	LC
21	<i>Oxyura jamaicensis</i>	Ruddy Duck	W	0-1200	P (u-c), C (u-c)	M	LC
	Cracidae	Guans & Curassows					
22	<i>Ortalis vetula</i>	Plain Chachalaca	DF, FE, SF	0-1300	P (c, l), C (u, l)	R	LC
23	<i>Ortalis cinereiceps</i>	Gray-headed Chachalaca	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1400	C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
24	<i>Ortalis leucogastra</i>	White-bellied Chachalaca	DF, FE, SF	0-500	P n (u, l)	R	LC
25	<i>Penelope purpurascens</i>	Crested Guan	DF, FE, SF	0-1300	P (r, l), C (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	NT
26	<i>Penelopina nigra</i>	Highland Guan	CF, FE	1100 +	C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	VU
27	<i>Crax rubra</i>	Great Curassow	WF, CF	0-1300	P (r, l), C (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	VU
	Odontophoridae	New World Quail					
28	<i>Rhynchortyx cinctus</i>	Tawny-faced Quail	WF	0-700	C (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	NT
29	<i>Dendrortyx leucophrys</i>	Buffy-crowned Wood-Partridge	PF, FE, CF, SF	1200 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
30	<i>Colinus nigrogularis</i>	Black-throated Bobwhite	PS	0-200	C n (c, l)	R	LC
31	<i>Colinus cristatus</i>	Crested Bobwhite	DF, S, FE, SF	0-1600	P (a), C (c, l)	R	LC
32	<i>Cyrtonyx ocellatus</i>	Ocellated Quail	PF	1000-1600	C (r, l)	R	VU
33	<i>Odontophorus melanotis</i>	Black-eared Wood-Quail	WF- FE	0-1000	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
34	<i>Odontophorus guttatus</i>	Spotted Wood-Quail	WF - CF	1000 +	C (u, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
	Podicipedidae	Grebes					
35	<i>Tachybaptus dominicus</i>	Least Grebe	W	0-1450	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
36	<i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>	Pied-billed Grebe	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
37	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	^N Eared Grebe	W	400	C sw (ac)	V	LC
	Columbidae	Pigeons & Doves					
38	<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock Pigeon	U	0-1500	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	IUCN
39	<i>Patagioenas cayennensis</i>	Pale-vented Pigeon	FE, SF, PS, W	0-300	Cb (c)	R	LC
40	<i>Patagioenas speciosa</i>	Scaled Pigeon	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1500	C (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
41	<i>Patagioenas leucocephala</i>	White-crowned Pigeon	W, O	0-50	Cb e (r, l), Cb i (a, l)	R	NT
42	<i>Patagioenas flavirostris</i>	Red-billed Pigeon	O, S, SF	0-2000	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
43	<i>Patagioenas fasciata</i>	Band-tailed Pigeon	PF, CF	1000 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
44	<i>Patagioenas nigrirostris</i>	Short-billed Pigeon	WF, FE, SF	0-1000	C (ac), Cb (c)	R	LC
45	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Eurasian Collared-Dove	O, U	0-50	P (u), C (mr), Cb (r)	R	LC
46	<i>Columbina inca</i>	Inca Dove	O, S, SF	0-1400	P (a), C (c), L w (u - c)	R	LC
47	<i>Columbina passerina</i>	Common Ground Dove	O, S, SF	0-1400	P (c), C (c)	R	LC
48	<i>Columbina minuta</i>	Plain-breasted Ground Dove	S, O, PS	0-1400	P (vr), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
49	<i>Columbina talpacoti</i>	Ruddy Ground Dove	O, S, EX	0-1500	P (a), C (c), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
50	<i>Claravis pretiosa</i>	Blue Ground Dove	FE, SF	0-1900	P n (r, l), P s L v (mr, l), C (e,l), Cb (c)	R	LC
51	<i>Paraclaravis mondetoura</i>	^N Maroon-chested Ground Dove	PF,CF	1800 +	C (vr, l)	R	LC
52	<i>Geotrygon montana</i>	Ruddy Quail-Dove	WF, PF	0-1400	P v (vr, l) C (u, l), Cb (c,l)	R	LC
53	<i>Geotrygon violacea</i>	Violaceous Quail-Dove	WF, CF	0-1400	C (vr, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
54	<i>Leptotrygon veraguensis</i>	Olive-backed Quail-Dove	WF	0-50	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
55	<i>Leptotila verreauxi</i>	White-tipped Dove	DF, SF, S, FE	0-1400	P (a), C (c), Cb (r, l)	R	LC
56	<i>Leptotila cassinii</i>	Gray-chested Dove	WF,CF	0-1400	C (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
57	<i>Leptotila plumbeiceps</i>	Gray-headed Dove	WF, CF, DF	0-1400	P (r,l), C (r,l), Cb (u)	R	LC
58	<i>Zentrygon albifacies</i>	White-faced Quail-Dove	CF, FE	1200 +	C (c, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
59	<i>Zenaida asiatica</i>	White-winged Dove	O, U	0-1500	P (a), C (c), Cb (u)	R, M	LC
60	<i>Zenaida macroura</i>	Mourning Dove	S, O	0-1500	P (c), C (u)	R, M	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UICN
	Cuculidae	Cuckoos					
61	<i>Crotophaga ani</i>	Smooth-billed Ani	O, SF	0-50	Cb i (c, l)	R	LC
62	<i>Crotophaga sulcirostris</i>	Groove-billed Ani	O, SF	0-1500	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
63	<i>Tapera naevia</i>	Striped Cuckoo	S, SF, O	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
64	<i>Dromococcyx phasianellus</i>	Pheasant Cuckoo	CF	700 +	P n v (ext?), C (c,l), Cb (r,l)	R	LC
65	<i>Morococcyx erythropygus</i>	Lesser Ground-Cuckoo	DF, SF, S, EX	0-1300	P (c), C (u), P so (r)	R	LC
66	<i>Geococcyx velox</i>	Lesser Roadrunner	PF, EX, S	500-1600	P n v (r), C (c,l), L ne (vr,l)	R	LC
67	<i>Neomorphus geoffroyi</i>	Rufous-vented Ground-Cuckoo	WF	0-900	C (ext?), Cb (r, l)	R	VU
68	<i>Piaya cayana</i>	Squirrel Cuckoo	WF, DF, CF, FE	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
69	<i>Coccyzus melacoryphus</i>	Dark-billed Cuckoo	WF, W	0-50	Cb s (ac)	V	LC
70	<i>Coccyzus americanus</i>	Yellow-billed Cuckoo	F, W	0-1350	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	PM	LC
71	<i>Coccyzus minor</i>	Mangrove Cuckoo	Mg, W, S	0-1300	P (c, l), C (u, l), Cb ne i (c, l)	PM, R	LC
72	<i>Coccyzus erythrophthalmus</i>	Black-billed Cuckoo	F, FE, SF, S, W	0-1350	P (u), C (u), L ne (u)	PM	LC
	Caprimulgidae	Nightjars & Allies					
73	<i>Lurocalis semitorquatus</i>	Short-tailed Nighthawk	WF, FE	0-500	Cb (r)	R	LC
74	<i>Chordeiles acutipennis</i>	Lesser Nighthawk	DF, PF, PS, W	0-1300	P (c), C (c - u), Cb (u)	R, M	LC
75	<i>Chordeiles minor</i>	Common Nighthawk	PS, DF, FE, EX	0-1300	P (u), C (r), Cb (c)	M, S	LC
76	<i>Nyctidromus albicollis</i>	Common Pauraque	DF, EX, S, FE, PF	0-1800	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
77	<i>Nyctiphrynus ocellatus</i>	Ocellated Poorwill	WF, CF	0-1300	C (r), Cb (r)	R	LC
78	<i>Antrostomus carolinensis</i>	Chuck-will's-widow	DF, FE, WF, SF	0-1300	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	M	NT
79	<i>Antrostomus rufus</i>	Rufous Nightjar	WF	0-100	CS (vr, l)	R	LC
80	<i>Antrostomus salvini</i>	Tawny-collared Nightjar	EX, S	1300	C (ac)	V	LC
81	<i>Antrostomus ridgwayi</i>	Buff-collared Nightjar	EX, S, O	100-800	C (r, l), Lnw (vr)	R	LC

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82	<i>Antrostomus vociferus</i>	Eastern Whip-poor-will	DF, S, SF	0-400	P (r), L e (r)	M	NT
83	<i>Antrostomus arizonae</i>	Mexican Whip-poor-will	PF	1400 +	C (r, l)	R	LC
84	<i>Hydropsalis maculicaudus</i>	Spot-tailed Nightjar	PS	0-100	Cb n (c,l)	S	LC
	Nyctibiidae	Potoos					
85	<i>Nyctibius grandis</i>	Great Potoo	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1400	C (vr, l), C (r, l)	R	LC
86	<i>Nyctibius griseus</i>	Common Potoo	WF	0-1000	Cb (r,l)	R	LC
87	<i>Nyctibius jamaicensis</i>	Northern Potoo	DF, PS, PF, EX, SF	0-1500	P (u, l), C (r, l), Cb n (r,l)	R	LC
	Apodidae	Swifts					
88	<i>Cypseloides niger</i>	Black Swift	DF, CF, WF	0-1600	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	PM, S	VU
89	<i>Cypseloides cryptus</i>	White-chinned Swift	CF, WF	100-1500	C (vr), Cb (r - c,l)	R, ?	LC
90	<i>Streptoprocne rutila</i>	Chestnut-collared Swift	CF, WF?	700 +	C (r), Cb (vr)	R	LC
91	<i>Streptoprocne zonaris</i>	White-collared Swift	F	0-1800	P (u), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
92	<i>Chaetura cinereiventris</i>	Gray-rumped Swift	WF	0-1500	P (r), C (r), Cb (u)	P	NT
93	<i>Chaetura pelagica</i>	Chimney Swift	F	0-1600	P s (c), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
94	<i>Chaetura vauxi</i>	Vaux's Swift	WF	0-600	Cb (c)	R	LC
95	<i>Panyptila cayennensis</i>	Lesser Swallow-tailed Swift	WF	0-600	Cb (r)	R	LC
96	<i>Panyptila sanctihieronymi</i>	Great Swallow-tailed Swift	CF	800 +	C (r)	R	LC
	Trochilidae	Hummingbirds					
97	<i>Florisuga mellivora</i>	White-necked Jacobin	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1300	P v (vr), C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
98	<i>Eutoxeres aquila</i>	White-tipped Sicklebill	WF	0-400	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
99	<i>Glaucis aeneus</i>	Bronzy Hermit	WF, SF, FE	0-700	C (ac), Cb (r - c,l)	R	LC
100	<i>Threnetes ruckeri</i>	Band-tailed Barbthroat	WF, SF, FE	0-600	C (ac), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
101	<i>Phaethornis longirostris</i>	Long-billed Hermit	CF, WF, FE, SF	0-1500	P s (vr, l), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
102	<i>Phaethornis striigularis</i>	Stripe-throated Hermit	CF, WF, FE, SF	0-1400	P s (u, l), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC

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103	<i>Colibri delphinae</i>	Brown Violetear	CF, PF, FE	1000 +	C (u, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
104	<i>Colibri thalassinus</i>	Mexican Violetear	CF, PF, FE	1200 +	P n, v (vr), C (u, l)	R	LC
105	<i>Heliostyris barroti</i>	Purple-crowned Fairy	WF, FE	0-700	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
106	<i>Anthracothorax prevostii</i>	Green-breasted Mango	DF, FE, SF	0-1000	P (c, l), C (u-c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
107	<i>Anthracothorax nigricollis</i>	Black-throated Mango	WF, FE	0-50	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
108	<i>Lophornis helenae</i>	Black-crested Coquette	CF, WF, FE, SF	0-1300	C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
109	<i>Eugenes fulgens</i>	Rivoli's Hummingbird	PF, CF, FE,	1300 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
110	<i>Heliomaster longirostris</i>	Long-billed Starthroat	WF, FE, SF	0-1300	P (ac), C (r, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
111	<i>Heliomaster constantii</i>	Plain-capped Starthroat	DF, FE, PF, SF, S	0-1300	P (c), C (u)	R	LC
112	<i>Lampornis sybillae</i>	Green-breasted Mountain-gem	CF, FE, PF	1000 +	C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
113	<i>Lampornis calolaemus</i>	Purple-throated Mountain-gem	CF	1100 +	P s v (c, l)	R	LC
114	<i>Tilmatura dupontii</i>	Sparkling-tailed Hummingbird	CF, PF, FE, SF	1100 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
115	<i>Archilochus colubris</i>	Ruby-throated Hummingbird	DF, FE, SF, S	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
116	<i>Cynanthus canivetii</i>	Canivet's Emerald	DF, SF, S, PS	0-1400	P (c), C (u), L se (r), Cb n (r)	R	LC
117	<i>Basilinna leucotis</i>	White-eared Hummingbird	PF, WF, FE, SF	1000 +	P n v (vr), C (c)	R	LC
118	<i>Abeillia abeillei</i>	Emerald-chinned Hummingbird	CF, FE, SF	1100 +	C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
119	<i>Klais guimeti</i>	Violet-headed Hummingbird	WF, FE	0-1400	C (ac), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
120	<i>Campylopterus hemileucurus</i>	Violet Sabrewing	CF, FE, SF	1000 +	C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
121	<i>Chalybura urochrysis</i>	Bronze-tailed Plumeleteer	WF, FE	0-800	Cb (r - c, l)	R	LC
122	<i>Thalurania colombica</i>	Crowned Woodnymph	WF, FE, SF	0-1300	L sw (vr, l), C (u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC

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123	<i>Microchera albocoronata</i>	Snowcap	WF, CF, FE	0-1200	C (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
124	<i>Eupherusa eximia</i>	Stripe-tailed Hummingbird	CF, FE, SF	800 +	C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
125	<i>Phaeochroa cuvierii</i>	Scaly-breasted Hummingbird	FE, SF	0-1300	C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
126	<i>Saucerottia cyanocephala</i>	Azure-crowned Hummingbird	PF, CF, PS	1000 +, 0-100	C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
127	<i>Saucerottia hoffmanni</i>	Blue-vented Hummingbird	DF, FE, SF, S	0-1300	C (u), P (c), L ne (u)	R	LC
128	<i>Saucerottia cyanura</i>	Blue-tailed Hummingbird	DF, FE, SF, S	0-1400	P (c, l), C (u, l, s), Cb (ac)	R	LC
129	<i>Amazilia rutila</i>	Cinnamon Hummingbird	SF, FE, S, DF	0-1400	P (a), C (c, l), Cb (r - u)	R	LC
130	<i>Amazilia tzacatl</i>	Rufous-tailed Hummingbird	FE, SF	0-1500	C (a), C (a)	R	LC
131	<i>Polyerata amabilis</i>	Blue-chested Hummingbird	FE, SF, R	0-300	C (ac), L s (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
132	<i>Chlorestes candida</i>	White-bellied Emerald	CF, WF, FE	0-1400	C (c, l, s), Cb (u, s)	R	LC
133	<i>Chlorestes eliciae</i>	Blue-throated Goldentail	DF, SF, FE	0-1300	P (c, l), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Rallidae	Rails, Crakes, & Gallinules					
134	<i>Pardirallus maculatus</i>	Spotted Rail	W,	0-450	P e (r, l), C sw (u, l) Cb (u, l)	R	LC
135	<i>Amaurolimnas concolor</i>	Uniform Crake	W, WF	0-800	C (ac), Cb (r)	R	LC
136	<i>Aramides axillaris</i>	Rufous-necked Wood-Rail	W, DF	0-800	P (u, l)	R	LC
137	<i>Aramides albiventris</i>	Russet-naped Wood-Rail	W, FE	0-1400	P s (r, l), C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
138	<i>Rallus longirostris</i>	Mangrove Rail	W	0-100	P n (c, l), P s (r)	R	LC
139	<i>Porzana carolina</i>	Sora	W	0-1300	P (r, l), C (u), Cb s (u)	M	LC
140	<i>Gallinula galeata</i>	Common Gallinule	W	0-1450	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R, M	LC
141	<i>Fulica americana</i>	American Coot	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R, M	LC
142	<i>Porphyrio martinicus</i>	Purple Gallinule	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
143	<i>Hapalocrex flaviventer</i>	Yellow-breasted Crake	W, FE	0-100	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
144	<i>Laterallus ruber</i>	Ruddy Crake	W, FE	0-1400	P (vr, l), C (u -c), Cb (c, l)	R	LC

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145	<i>Laterallus albigularis</i>		White-throated Crake	W, FE	0-400	C (ac), L s, se (u, l), (Cb (c))	R	LC
146	<i>Laterallus exilis</i>		Gray-breasted Crake	W, FE	0-200	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
147	<i>Laterallus jamaicensis</i>	N	Black Rail	W	0-100	Cb n (vr)	M	EN
	Heliornithidae		Finfoots					
148	<i>Heliornis fulica</i>		Sungrebe	W, WF	0-200	P, L w (ac), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
	Aramidae		Limpkin					
149	<i>Aramus guarauna</i>		Limpkin	W	0-450	P (c, l), C sw (r, l), Cb n (r), Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
	Burhinidae		Thick-knees					
150	<i>Burhinus bistriatus</i>		Double-striped Thick-knee	O, DF, FE	0-700	P (c, l), L (c, l), C w (r)	R	LC
	Recurvirostridae		Stilts & Avocets					
151	<i>Himantopus mexicanus</i>		Black-necked Stilt	W	0-1400	P (a), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
152	<i>Recurvirostra americana</i>		American Avocet	W	0-450	P (u, l), C sw (r, l)	M	LC
	Haematopodidae		Oystercatchers					
153	<i>Haematopus palliatus</i>		American Oystercatcher	W	0-50	P (u - c), Cb (r)	M, R	LC
	Charadriidae		Plovers & Lapwings					
154	<i>Vanellus chilensis</i>		Southern Lapwing	W, O	0-1400	P (c), C (r), Cb (u)	R	LC
155	<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>		Black-bellied Plover	W	0-450	P (c), C sw (r, l), Cb (u - c)	M	LC
156	<i>Pluvialis dominica</i>		American Golden-Plover	W	0-50	P (r)	PM	LC
157	<i>Pluvialis fulva</i>		Pacific Golden-Plover	W	0-50	P (ac)	V	LC
158	<i>Charadrius vociferus</i>		Killdeer	W	0-1200	P (a), C (u - c), Cb (u)	M, R	LC
159	<i>Charadrius semipalmatus</i>		Semipalmated Plover	W	0-450	P (c), C sw (u, l), Cb (u)	M	LC
160	<i>Charadrius melodus</i>		Piping Plover	W	0-50	Cb (ac)	V	NT
161	<i>Charadrius wilsonia</i>		Wilson's Plover	W	0-100	P (u), Cb (r)	R, M	LC

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162	<i>Charadrius collaris</i>		Collared Plover	W	0-1000	P (c), C (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
163	<i>Charadrius nivosus</i>		Snowy Plover	W	0-50	P (r - u, l)	M	NT
	Jacaniidae		Jacanas					
164	<i>Jacana spinosa</i>		Northern Jacana	W	0-1300	P (a), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
165	<i>Jacana jacana</i>		Wattled Jacana	W	0-1000	C (ac), Cb (ac)	V	LC
	Scolopacidae		Sandpipers & Allies					
166	<i>Bartramia longicauda</i>		Upland Sandpiper	W	0-1300	P (r), C (vr), Cb (vr)	PM	LC
167	<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>		Whimbrel	W	0-50	P (a), Cb (r)	M	LC
168	<i>Numenius americanus</i>		Long-billed Curlew	W	0	P (r - u)	M	LC
169	<i>Limosa haemastica</i>	N	Hudsonian Godwit	W	0-50	P (vr), C sw (r, l), Cb i (ac)	PM	LC
170	<i>Limosa fedoa</i>		Marbled Godwit	W	0-50	P (u)	M	LC
171	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>		Ruddy Turnstone	W	0-50	P (c), Cb (r)	M	LC
172	<i>Arenaria melanocephala</i>	N	Black Turnstone	W	0	P nw (ac)	V	LC
173	<i>Calidris canutus</i>		Red Knot	W	0	P (r)	M	NT
174	<i>Calidris virgata</i>		Surfbird	W	0-50	P (u)	M	LC
175	<i>Calidris pugnax</i>	N	Ruff	W	? - 450	C so (ac)	V	LC
176	<i>Calidris himantopus</i>		Stilt Sandpiper	W	0-450	P (c - a), C sw (u, l)	M	LC
177	<i>Calidris alba</i>		Sanderling	W	0-1000	P (u), C (ac), Cb (r)	M	LC
178	<i>Calidris alpina</i>		Dunlin	W	0	P (vr)	M	LC
179	<i>Calidris bairdii</i>		Baird's Sandpiper	W	0-1000	P (vr), C (vr)	PM	LC
180	<i>Calidris minutilla</i>		Least Sandpiper	W	0-1000	P (c), C (u, l), Cb (r)	M	LC
181	<i>Calidris fuscicollis</i>		White-rumped Sandpiper	W	0-50	P (r), Cb s (vr l)	PM	LC
182	<i>Calidris subruficollis</i>		Buff-breasted Sandpiper	W	0-1000	P (vr), C (vr, l)	PM	NT
183	<i>Calidris melanotos</i>		Pectoral Sandpiper	W	0-1300	P (u-c), C (u, l), Cb (vr, l)	PM	LC
184	<i>Calidris pusilla</i>		Semipalmated Sandpiper	W	0-450	P (c - u, l), C sw (ac), Cb (vr)	M	NT

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185	<i>Calidris mauri</i>		Western Sandpiper	W	0-450	P (c), C sw (r, l), Cb (r)	M	LC
186	<i>Limnodromus griseus</i>		Short-billed Dowitcher	W	0-450	P (c), C sw (r, l), Cb i (ac)	M	LC
187	<i>Limnodromus scolopaceus</i>		Long-billed Dowitcher	W	0-450	P (u), C sw (u, l), Cb n (c, l)	M	LC
188	<i>Gallinago delicata</i>		Wilson's Snipe	W	0-1300	P (r), C (r), Cb (ac)	M	LC
189	<i>Actitis macularius</i>		Spotted Sandpiper	W	0-1300	P (c), C (c-u), Cb (c)	M	LC
190	<i>Tringa solitaria</i>		Solitary Sandpiper	W	0-1300	P (c - u), C (u - r), Cb (u - r)	M	LC
191	<i>Tringa incana</i>		Wandering Tattler	W	0-50	P (r)	M	LC
192	<i>Tringa flavipes</i>		Lesser Yellowlegs	W	0-1000	P (a), C sw (c), C n (ac), Cb (r)	M	LC
193	<i>Tringa semipalmata</i>		Willet	W	0-50	P (a), Cb (r)	M	LC
194	<i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>		Greater Yellowlegs	W	0-1000	P (c), C (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
195	<i>Phalaropus tricolor</i>		Wilson's Phalarope	W	0-450	P (u), C sw (r)	PM	LC
196	<i>Phalaropus lobatus</i>		Red-necked Phalarope	P	0	P (c - r)	PM, P	LC
197	<i>Phalaropus fulicarius</i>		Red Phalarope	P	0	P (c - r), Cb se (vr)	PM, P	LC
	Stercorariidae		Skuas & Jaegers					
198	<i>Stercorarius pomarinus</i>		Pomarine Jaeger	P	0	P (c), Cb (u)	P, M	LC
199	<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>		Parasitic Jaeger	P	0	P (c), Cb (u)	P, M	LC
200	<i>Stercorarius longicaudus</i>		Long-tailed Jaeger	P	0	P (r), Cb i (vr)	P, M	LC
	Laridae		Gulls, Terns & Skimmers					
201	<i>Creagrus furcatus</i>		Swallow-tailed Gull	P	0	P (ac)	V, P	LC
202	<i>Xema sabini</i>		Sabine's Gull	P	0	P (c)	PM, P	LC
203	<i>Chroicocephalus philadelphia</i>	N	Bonaparte's Gull	P	0	P (ac)	V	LC
204	<i>Leucophaeus atricilla</i>		Laughing Gull	W	0-1000	P (c), C (u, l), Cb (c)	M	LC

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205	<i>Leucophaeus pipixcan</i>	Franklin's Gull	W	0-50	P (u), Cb (ac)	PM, M	LC
206	<i>Larus delawarensis</i>	Ring-billed Gull	W	0	P (vr), Cb (vr)	M	LC
207	<i>Larus californicus</i>	California Gull	W	0	P (ac)	V	LC
208	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Herring Gull	W	0-50	P (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
209	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Lesser Black-backed Gull	W	0	P (ac), Cb (ac)	V	LC
210	<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	Kelp Gull	W	0-50	P L nw (ac)	V	LC
211	<i>Anous stolidus</i>	Brown Noddy	P	0	P (u), Cb (u)	P	LC
212	<i>Onychoprion fuscatus</i>	Sooty Tern	P	0	P (ac), Cb (ac)	V	LC
213	<i>Onychoprion anaethetus</i>	Bridled Tern	P	0	P (r -u, l), Cb (u)	M, R	LC
214	<i>Sternula antillarum</i>	Least Tern	W	0-50	P (a, l - u), Cb (u)	PM, R	LC
215	<i>Phaetusa simplex</i>	Large-billed Tern	W	0-50	L nw, sw (ac), Cb (ac)	V	LC
216	<i>Gelochelidon nilotica</i>	Gull-billed Tern	W	0-50	P (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
217	<i>Hydroprogne caspia</i>	Caspian Tern	W	0-50	P (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
218	<i>Chlidonias niger</i>	Black Tern	W	0-50	P (c), Cb (r)	M, PM	LC
219	<i>Sterna dougallii</i>	Roseate Tern	P	0	Cb (ac)	V, P	LC
220	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Common Tern	W	0-50	P (c), Cb (u)	M	LC
221	<i>Sterna paradisaea</i>	Arctic Tern	P	0	P (vr), Cb (ac)	P, PM	LC
222	<i>Sterna forsteri</i>	Forster's Tern	W	0-50	P (u), Cb (ac)	M	LC
223	<i>Thalasseus maximus</i>	Royal Tern	W	0-50	P (a), Cb (a)	M	LC
224	<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>	Sandwich Tern	W	0-50	P (u), Cb (u)	M	LC
225	<i>Thalasseus elegans</i>	Elegant Tern	W	0-50	P (u), Cb s (ac)	M	NT
226	<i>Rynchops niger</i>	Black Skimmer	W	0-50	P (a - l, u), Cb s (r)	M	LC
	Eurypygidae	Sunbittern					
227	<i>Eurypyga helias</i>	Sunbittern	WF, W	0-1200	L s (vr), C (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC

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	Phaethontidae	Tropicbirds					
228	<i>Phaethon aethereus</i>	Red-billed Tropicbird	P	0	P (u - vr)	P, M	LC
	Hydrobatidae	Storm-Petrels					
229	<i>Hydrobates leucorhous</i>	Leach's Storm-Petrel	P	0	P (u)	P, M	NT
230	<i>Hydrobates tethys</i>	Wedge-rumped Storm-Petrel	P	0	P (c)	P, M	LC
231	<i>Hydrobates melania</i>	Black Storm-Petrel	P	0	P (u, l)	P, M	LC
232	<i>Hydrobates microsoma</i>	Least Storm-Petrel	P	0	P (u, l)	P, M	LC
	Procellariidae	Shearwaters & Petrels					
233	<i>Pterodroma hasitata</i>	Black-capped Petrel	P	0	Cb (ac)	P, V	EN
234	<i>Procellaria parkinsoni</i>	Parkinson's Petrel	P	0	P (u)	P, M	VU
235	<i>Ardenna pacifica</i>	Wedge-tailed Shearwater	P	0	P (c)	P, M	LC
236	<i>Ardenna creatopus</i>	Pink-footed Shearwater	P	0	P (c)	P, PM	VU
237	<i>Puffinus subalaris</i>	Galapagos Shearwater	P	0	P (c)	P, M	LC
238	<i>Puffinus opisthomelas</i>	Black-vented Shearwater	P	0	P (vr)	P, M	NT
239	<i>Puffinus lherminieri</i>	N Audubon's Shearwater	P	0	Cb (vr)	P, M	LC
	Ciconiidae	Storks					
240	<i>Jabiru mycteria</i>	Jabiru	W	0-450	P (r), C sw (r, l), Cb (r - c, l)	R	LC
241	<i>Mycteria americana</i>	Wood Stork	W	0-1300	P (a), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
	Fregatidae	Frigatebirds					
242	<i>Fregata magnificens</i>	Magnificent Frigatebird	W	0-50	P (a), Cb (c)	R	LC

	Species		Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	IUCN
	Sulidae		Boobies					
243	<i>Sula dactylatra</i>		Masked Booby	P	0	P (c), Cb (r)	P, M	LC
244	<i>Sula granti</i>		Nazca Booby	P	0	P (u)	P, M	LC
245	<i>Sula nebouxii</i>		Blue-footed Booby	P	0	P (vr, c - l)	P, M, R	LC
246	<i>Sula leucogaster</i>		Brown Booby	P	0	P (a), Cb (u)	P, R	LC
247	<i>Sula sula</i>		Red-footed Booby	P	0	P (u), Cb (r)	P, M	LC
	Anhingidae		Darters					
248	<i>Anhinga anhinga</i>		Anhinga	W	0-400	P (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
	Phalacrocoracidae		Cormorants					
249	<i>Nannopterum auritum</i>	N	Double-crested Cormorant	W	0	Cb (ac)	V	LC
250	<i>Nannopterum brasilianum</i>		Neotropic Cormorant	W	0-1300	P (a), C (a, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
	Pelecanidae		Pelicans					
251	<i>Pelecanus erythrorhynchos</i>		American White Pelican	W	0-50	P (c), Cb s (vr)	R	LC
252	<i>Pelecanus occidentalis</i>		Brown Pelican	W	0-100	P (a), Cb (c)	M	LC
	Ardeidae		Hérons, Egrets & Bitterns					
253	<i>Botaurus pinnatus</i>		Pinnated Bittern	W	0-1000	P (r), C (r), Cb (r)	R	LC
254	<i>Botaurus lentiginosus</i>		American Bittern	W	0-1000	C (ac), Cb s (ac)	V, M	LC
255	<i>Ixobrychus exilis</i>		Least Bittern	W	0-1000	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
256	<i>Tigrisoma lineatum</i>		Rufescent Tiger-Heron	WF, W	0-50	Cb (r - u)	R	LC
257	<i>Tigrisoma fasciatum</i>		Fasciated Tiger-Heron	W	0-50	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
258	<i>Tigrisoma mexicanum</i>		Bare-throated Tiger-Heron	W	0-450	P (u), L (c), C sw (r, l), Cb (u)	R	LC

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259	<i>Ardea herodias</i>	Great Blue Heron	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
260	<i>Ardea alba</i>	Great Egret	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R, M	LC
261	<i>Egretta thula</i>	Snowy Egret	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
262	<i>Egretta caerulea</i>	Little Blue Heron	W	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M, R	LC
263	<i>Egretta tricolor</i>	Tricolored Heron	W	0-1000	P (c), C sw (c), C (u), Cb (u)	R, M	LC
264	<i>Egretta rufescens</i>	Reddish Egret	W	0	P (u), Cb (r)	R, M	NT
265	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle Egret	W, O	0-1400	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
266	<i>Butorides virescens</i>	Green Heron	W	0-1400	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R, M	LC
267	<i>Butorides striata</i>	Striated Heron	W	0-50	Cb s (ac)	V	LC
268	<i>Agamia agami</i>	Agami Heron	W	0-50	L s (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	VU
269	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Black-crowned Night-Heron	W	0-1000	P (c), C (r), Cb (c)	R, M	LC
270	<i>Nyctanassa violacea</i>	Yellow-crowned Night-Heron	W	0-1000	P (u), C (ac), Cb (c)	R, M	LC
271	<i>Cochlearius cochlearius</i>	Boat-billed Heron	W	0-500	P (u-c, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Threskiornithidae	Ibises & Spoonbills					
272	<i>Eudocimus albus</i>	White Ibis	W	0-450	P (c, l), C sw (u, l), Cb (r, l)	R	LC
273	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>	Glossy Ibis	W	0-450	P (u), C sw (u, l), L s (u, l), Cb s (u, l)	M, R	LC
274	<i>Plegadis chihi</i>	N White-faced Ibis	W	0-450	P (vr), C sw (r, l)	M, V	LC
275	<i>Mesembrinibis cayennensis</i>	Green Ibis	W	0-100	L s (u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
276	<i>Platalea ajaja</i>	Roseate Spoonbill	W	0-1000	P (c, l), C (u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
	Cathartidae	New World Vultures					
277	<i>Sarcoramphus papa</i>	King Vulture	WF, DF, CF, PF	0-1900	P (r), C (r, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
278	<i>Coragyps atratus</i>	Black Vulture	O	0-2000	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
279	<i>Cathartes aura</i>	Turkey Vulture	O	0-2000	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R, M	LC

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280	<i>Cathartes burrovianus</i>	Lesser Yellow-headed Vulture	W	0-450	P (r, l), L (u, l), C sw (acc), Cb (u)	R	LC
	Pandionidae	Osprey					
281	<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>	Osprey	W	0-1300	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	M	LC
	Accipitridae	Hawks, Kites & Eagles					
282	<i>Gampsonyx swainsonii</i>	Pearl Kite	O	0-800	P (c), C w (u), Cb w (r)	R	LC
283	<i>Elanus leucurus</i>	White-tailed Kite	O	0-1350	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
284	<i>Chondrohierax uncinatus</i>	Hook-billed Kite	F, FE, SF	0-1400	P (r), C (u - c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
285	<i>Leptodon cayanensis</i>	Gray-headed Kite	DF, FE, WF, SF	0-500	P (u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
286	<i>Elanoides forficatus</i>	Swallow-tailed Kite	CF, FE, WF	0-1900	P (r), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	S, P/S	LC
287	<i>Morphnus guianensis</i>	Crested Eagle	WF	0-300	Cb (vr, l)	R	NT
288	<i>Harpia harpyja</i>	Harpy Eagle	WF	0-500	C (ext?), Cb (vr, l)	R	VU
289	<i>Spizaetus tyrannus</i>	Black Hawk-Eagle	WF, CF	0-2000	P (vr), C (u, l), Cb (r)	R	LC
290	<i>Spizaetus melanoleucus</i>	Black-and-white Hawk-Eagle	WF	0-1000	Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
291	<i>Spizaetus ornatus</i>	Ornate Hawk-Eagle	WF, CF, PF	0-1300	C (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	NT
292	<i>Harpagus bidentatus</i>	Double-toothed Kite	CF, WF, DF, FE	0-1400	P s (vr, l), C (u), Cb (r)	R	LC
293	<i>Circus hudsonius</i>	Northern Harrier	O, W, S	0-1400	P (c), L s (c), C (u), Cb (u)	M	LC
294	<i>Accipiter superciliosus</i>	Tiny Hawk	WF, FE, SF	0-200	Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
295	<i>Accipiter striatus</i>	Sharp-shinned Hawk	PF, FE, SF	0-1500	P (r), C (u - c, l), Cb s (r, l)	R, M	LC
296	<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	Cooper's Hawk	FE, O, SF	0-1300	P (vr), C (u), Cb (vr)	M	LC
297	<i>Accipiter bicolor</i>	Bicolored Hawk	F, FE, SF	0-1300	C (r), Cb (vr)	R	LC
298	<i>Ictinia mississippiensis</i>	Mississippi Kite	O, F, FE, SF, S	0-1400	P (u), C (c), Cb (r)	PM	LC
299	<i>Ictinia plumbea</i>	Plumbeous Kite	F, FE	0-1400	P (r), C (u), Cb (r)	S	LC
300	<i>Busarellus nigricollis</i>	Black-collared Hawk	W	0-100	P (u, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC

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301	<i>Geranospiza caerulescens</i>	Crane Hawk	W, F, FE	0-1200	P (r,l) C (vr), Cb (u,l)	R	LC
302	<i>Rostrhamus sociabilis</i>	Snail Kite	W	0-1000	P (c,l), C sw (r, l), C n (vr,l), Cb s (c,l)	R	LC
303	<i>Buteogallus anthracinus</i>	Common Black Hawk	W, WF, O	0-1400	P (c,l), C (r,l), Cb (c,l)	R	LC
304	<i>Buteogallus meridionalis</i>	Savanna Hawk	O	0-100	P, (ac)	V	LC
305	<i>Buteogallus urubitinga</i>	Great Black Hawk	F, FE, PF, SF, S, W	0-1300	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
306	<i>Buteogallus solitarius</i>	Solitary Eagle	F, PF	400-1300	C (vr,l) Cb (r, l)	R	NT
307	<i>Morphnarchus princeps</i>	Barred Hawk	F	400-1650	Cb (vr,l)	R	LC
308	<i>Rupornis magnirostris</i>	Roadside Hawk	SF, FE, S, O	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
309	<i>Parabuteo unicinctus</i>	Harris's Hawk	DF, SF, EX, S, W	0-1000	P (u), C (vr), Cb s (u)	R	LC
310	<i>Geranoaetus albicaudatus</i>	White-tailed Hawk	O, S, EX, PS	0-1400	P (u), C (u,l), Cb n (c, l), Cb s (vr)	R	LC
311	<i>Pseudastur albicollis</i>	White Hawk	WF, FE	0-1200	P s (vr), C e (r), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
312	<i>Leucopternis semiplumbeus</i>	Semiplumbeous Hawk	WF, FE, SF, R	0-100	Cb n (vr), Cb s (u, l)	R	LC
313	<i>Buteo plagiatus</i>	Gray Hawk	F, FE, SF, O	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
314	<i>Buteo platypterus</i>	Broad-winged Hawk	F, FE, SF	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	M	LC
315	<i>Buteo brachyurus</i>	Short-tailed Hawk	DF, WF, PF, FE	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
316	<i>Buteo swainsoni</i>	Swainson's Hawk	DF, WF, FE, SF, O	0-1500	P (r), C (a), Cb (r)	M, PM	LC
317	<i>Buteo albonotatus</i>	Zone-tailed Hawk	O, SF, S	0-1400	P (u), C (r), Cb (r)	R, M	LC
318	<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	Red-tailed Hawk	PF, PS, SF, S, O	0-1600	P (r), C (u), Cb n (r), Cb s (vr)	R, M	LC
	Tytonidae	Barn-Owls					
319	<i>Tyto alba</i>	Barn Owl	O, U, W, FE, SF	0-1600	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC

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	Strigidae	Owls					
320	<i>Megascops trichopsis</i>	Whiskered Screech-Owl	PF	750-1500	P (vr, l), C (r, l)	R	LC
321	<i>Megascops cooperi</i>	Pacific Screech-Owl	DF, PF, EX, SF	0-800	P (c), C (u, l), Cb nw (u, l)	R	LC
322	<i>Megascops guatemalae</i>	Middle American Screech-Owl	WF, CF, FE	0-1400	C (r,l), Cb (r, l)	R	LC
323	<i>Lophotrix cristata</i>	Crested Owl	CF, WF	0-1400	C u (u,l), Cb (u,l)	R	LC
324	<i>Pulsatrix perspicillata</i>	Spectacled Owl	DF, WF, CF, FE	0-1500	P (u, l), C (r,l), Cb (u)	R	LC
325	<i>Bubo virginianus</i>	Great Horned Owl	DF, EX, FE, PF, PS	200-1600	P n (r,l), C (r,l), Cb (r,l)	R	LC
326	<i>Glaucidium gnoma</i>	Northern Pygmy-Owl	PF, CF, FE, SF	1000 +	C n (vr, l)	R	LC
327	<i>Glaucidium griseiceps</i>	Central American Pygmy-Owl	WF, R, SF	0-700	Cb (u)	R	LC
328	<i>Glaucidium brasilianum</i>	Ferruginous Pygmy-Owl	DF, SF, FE, S, EX	0-1500	P (a), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
329	<i>Athene cunicularia</i>	Burrowing Owl	O, S, EX	? - 1500	C (ac)	M, V	LC
330	<i>Ciccaba virgata</i>	Mottled Owl	DF, CF, WF, FE	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
331	<i>Ciccaba nigrolineata</i>	Black-and-white Owl	CF, WF, PF, FE	0-1500	P (vr - ac, l), C (u, l) Cb (r)	R	LC
332	<i>Asio stygius</i>	Stygian Owl	CF, FE	1200 +	C (vr, l)	R	LC
333	<i>Asio flammeus</i>	N Short-eared Owl	O, W	0-450	C sw (acc)	V	LC
334	<i>Asio clamator</i>	Striped Owl	O, S, EX, FE, R	0-1000	P (r), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Trogonidae	Trogons					
335	<i>Trogon clathratus</i>	Lattice-tailed Trogon	WF, FE, R	0-400	Cb sw (vr - ac)	R	LC
336	<i>Trogon massena</i>	Slaty-tailed Trogon	WF, FE, SF	0-1000	P se (vr), C u (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
337	<i>Trogon melanocephalus</i>	Black-headed Trogon	DF, SC, FE, S	0-1300	P (c), C (u), C e (r), Cb (u)	R	LC
338	<i>Trogon caligatus</i>	Gartered Trogon	F, FE, SF	0-1350	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
339	<i>Trogon rufus</i>	Black-throated Trogon	WF, FE, R	0-1000	C e (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC

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340	<i>Trogon elegans</i>	Elegant Trogon	DF, EX, SF, R	0-1350	P (u, l), C w (u, l)	R	LC
341	<i>Trogon collaris</i>	Collared Trogon	CF, WF, FE	800 +	C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
342	<i>Pharomachrus mocinno</i>	Resplendent Quetzal	CF, WF	1000 +	C (r, l), Cb nw (u, l)	R	NT
	Momotidae	Motmots					
343	<i>Hylomanes momotula</i>	Tody Motmot	F	300-1000	C (ext?), Cb n (u, l)	R	LC
344	<i>Momotus lessonii</i>	Lesson's Motmot	DF, CF, WF, FE	0-1800	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
345	<i>Baryphthengus martii</i>	Rufous Motmot	WF	0-1000	C e (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
346	<i>Electron carinatum</i>	Keel-billed Motmot	WF	200-1200	C e (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	VU
347	<i>Electron platyrhynchum</i>	Broad-billed Motmot	WF	0-1000	C e (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
348	<i>Eumomota superciliosa</i>	Turquoise-browed Motmot	DF, FE, SF, S, U	0-1500	P (a), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
	Alcedinidae	Kingfishers					
349	<i>Megaceryle torquata</i>	Ringed Kingfisher	W, R	0-1000	P (c, l), C (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
350	<i>Megaceryle alcyon</i>	Belted Kingfisher	W, R	0-1200	P (c, l), C (u), Cb (c, l)	M	LC
351	<i>Chloroceryle amazona</i>	Amazon Kingfisher	W, R	0-1000	P (c, l), C (u), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
352	<i>Chloroceryle aenea</i>	American Pygmy Kingfisher	W, R	0-100	P (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
353	<i>Chloroceryle americana</i>	Green Kingfisher	W, R	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
354	<i>Chloroceryle inda</i>	Green-and-rufous Kingfisher	W, R, WF	0-100	Cb (r, l)	R	LC
	Bucconidae	Puffbirds and Nunbird					
355	<i>Notharchus hyperrhynchus</i>	White-necked Puffbird	DF, WF, FE, SF	0-450	P (c, l), C sw (vr, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
356	<i>Notharchus tectus</i>	Pied Puffbird	WF, FE, SF	0-100	Cb s (u, l)	R	LC
357	<i>Malacoptila panamensis</i>	White-whiskered Puffbird	WF	0-800	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
358	<i>Monasa morphoeus</i>	White-fronted Nunbird	WF	0-900	C e (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC

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	Galbulidae	Jacamars					
359	<i>Galbula ruficauda</i>	Rufous-tailed Jacamar	CF, WF, R	0-1300	C e (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
360	<i>Jacamerops aureus</i>	Great Jacamar	WF, R	0-600	Cb (c,l)	R	LC
	Ramphastidae	Toucans					
361	<i>Aulacorhynchus prasinus</i>	Northern Emerald-Toucanet	CF, PF, FE	1000 +	C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
362	<i>Pteroglossus torquatus</i>	Collared Aracari	F, FE, SF	0-1350	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
363	<i>Selenidera spectabilis</i>	Yellow-eared Toucanet	WF	300-1200	C e (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
364	<i>Ramphastos sulfuratus</i>	Keel-billed Toucan	CF, WF, DF, FE	0-1500	P (vr, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	NT
365	<i>Ramphastos ambiguus</i>	Yellow-throated Toucan	WF, CF	0-1000	C (vr, l), Cb (c, l)	R	NT
	Picidae	Woodpeckers					
366	<i>Picumnus olivaceus</i>	Olivaceous Piculet	SF, FE	0-1000	C (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
367	<i>Melanerpes formicivorus</i>	Acorn Woodpecker	PF, PS	600 +; 0-100	C (c, l), Cb ne (u, l)	R	LC
368	<i>Melanerpes pucherani</i>	Black-cheeked Woodpecker	WF, FE, SF	0-1300	C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
369	<i>Melanerpes hoffmannii</i>	Hoffmann's Woodpecker	SF, DF, EX	0-1300	P (a), C (u), Cb w (r)	R	LC
370	<i>Melanerpes aurifrons</i>	Golden-fronted Woodpecker	SF, FE, S	300 +	C (e), Cb nw (r)	R	LC
371	<i>Sphyrapicus varius</i>	Yellow-bellied Sapsucker	PF, PS, FE	0-1500	P (r), C (u), Cb (u)	M	LC
372	<i>Dryobates scalaris</i>	Ladder-backed Woodpecker	Mg, SP	0-50	P (u, l), Cb ne (r, l)	R	LC
373	<i>Dryobates villosus</i>	Hairy Woodpecker	PF, CF, FE	1200 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
374	<i>Dryobates fumigatus</i>	Smoky-brown Woodpecker	CF, WF, FE, SF	0-1500	P (vr, l), C (c), Cb (c,l)	R	LC
375	<i>Piculus simplex</i>	Rufous-winged Woodpecker	WF	0-800	C u (ac), Cb (u)	R	LC
376	<i>Colaptes rubiginosus</i>	Golden-olive Woodpecker	CF, PF, WF, SF, FE	0-1500	P (u, l), C (c), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
377	<i>Colaptes auratus</i>	Northern Flicker	PF, CF	1000 +	C (c, l)	R	LC
378	<i>Celeus loricatus</i>	Cinnamon Woodpecker	WF, FE	0-1000	Cb (u - r, l)	R	LC

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379	<i>Celeus castaneus</i>	Chestnut-colored Woodpecker	WF, FE	0-1200	C u (vr), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
380	<i>Dryocopus lineatus</i>	Lineated Woodpecker	F, SF	0-1700	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
381	<i>Campephilus guatemalensis</i>	Pale-billed Woodpecker	F, SF, FE	0-1500	P (u), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
	Falconidae	Falcons and Caracaras					
382	<i>Herpetotheres cachinnans</i>	Laughing Falcon	SF, FE, O	0-1450	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
383	<i>Micrastur ruficollis</i>	Barred Forest-Falcon	CF, WF	0-1400	C (u, l), Cb (r, l)	R	LC
384	<i>Micrastur mirandollei</i>	Slaty-backed Forest-Falcon	WF	0-800	Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
385	<i>Micrastur semitorquatus</i>	Collared Forest-Falcon	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
386	<i>Ibycter americanus</i>	Red-throated Caracara	WF, PS, FE	0-200	Cb (r, l)	R	LC
387	<i>Caracara plancus</i>	Crested Caracara	O, W, S	0-1600	P (c), C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
388	<i>Milvago chimachima</i>	Yellow-headed Caracara	O, W, R	0-1000	P (r), C (r, l), Cb n (r, l), Cb s (u, l)	R	LC
389	<i>Falco sparverius</i>	American Kestrel	O, W	0-1600	P (c), C (u), Cb (r)	M, R	LC
390	<i>Falco columbarius</i>	Merlin	O, W	0-1600	P (c), C (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
391	<i>Falco femoralis</i>	Aplomado Falcon	PS	0-100	P (ac), Cb n (u, l), Cb s (r)	R	LC
392	<i>Falco ruficularis</i>	Bat Falcon	PS, FE, O, SF, R, W	0-1600	P (r), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
393	<i>Falco deiroleucus</i>	Orange-breasted Falcon	F	0-?	C (ext?), Cb n (ext?)	R	NT
394	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	Peregrine Falcon	O, W, R	0-1300	P (u), C (u), Cb (r)	M	LC
	Psittacidae	Parrots					
395	<i>Eupsittula nana</i>	Olive-throated Parakeet	FE, SF, WF, CF	0-1300	C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
396	<i>Eupsittula canicularis</i>	Orange-fronted Parakeet	SF, S, EX	0-1400	P (a), C (c), Cb w (u)	R	VU
397	<i>Ara macao</i>	Scarlet Macaw	DF, WF, CF	0-1000	P n (u, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC

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398	<i>Ara ambiguus</i>	Great Green Macaw	WF, FE	0-500	Cb (u, l)	R	CR
399	<i>Psittacara holochlorus rubritorquis</i>	Green Parakeet	PF, CF	900 +	C n (a, l), C s (u, l)	R	LC
400	<i>Psittacara strenuus</i>	Pacific Parakeet	DF, FE, SF, EX	0-400	P n (a)	R	LC
401	<i>Psittacara finschi</i>	Crimson-fronted Parakeet	DF, FE, EX, U	0-1500	P (u), C (c), Cb (a)	R	LC
402	<i>Bolborhynchus lineola</i>	Barred Parakeet	CF	1300 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
403	<i>Brotogeris jugularis</i>	Orange-chinned Parakeet	SF, EX, FE, U	0-1300	P (a), C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
404	<i>Pyrrhula haematotis</i>	Brown-hooded Parrot	WF, CF, FE	0-1500	C e (r), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
405	<i>Pionus menstruus</i>	Blue-headed Parrot	WF, R	0-50	Cb s (vr)	R	LC
406	<i>Pionus senilis</i>	White-crowned Parrot	WF, CF, DF	0-1500	P s (u, l), C e (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
407	<i>Amazona albifrons</i>	White-fronted Parrot	FE, SF, S, EX	0-1900	P (a), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
408	<i>Amazona autumnalis</i>	Red-lored Parrot	WF, FE, SF	0-1300	P s (r, l), C e (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
409	<i>Amazona farinosa</i>	Mealy Parrot	WF, FE	0-600	C (ac), Cb (c)	R	LC
410	<i>Amazona auropalliata</i>	Yellow-naped Parrot	DF, PS, FE, SF	0-900	P (c), Cb n (c)	R	VU
	Pipridae	Manakins					
411	<i>Chiroxiphia linearis</i>	Long-tailed Manakin	DF, R, SF	0-1300	P (c, l), C (u, l), Cb sw L (r, l)	R	LC
412	<i>Corapipo altera</i>	White-ruffed Manakin	WF, CF	600 +	C e (r, l), Cb n (c, l), Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
413	<i>Manacus candei</i>	White-collared Manakin	FE, SF, WF	0-1200	C e (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
414	<i>Ceratopipra mentalis</i>	Red-capped Manakin	WF, CF	0-1300	C e (u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
	Cotingidae	Cotingas					
415	<i>Querula purpurata</i>	Purple-throated Fruitcrow	WF, R	0-400	Cb se (u, l)	R	LC
416	<i>Cephalopterus glabricollis</i>	Bare-necked Umbrellabird	WF, R	0-400	Cb se (vr)	R	LC
417	<i>Cotinga amabilis</i>	Lovely Cotinga	WF, FE	500-1200	Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
418	<i>Lipaugus unirufus</i>	Rufous Piha	WF	0-1000	C e (vr, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
419	<i>Procnias tricarunculatus</i>	Three-wattled Bellbird	CF	1000 +	C e (u, l), Cb nw (c)	R	VU

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420	<i>Carpodectes nitidus</i>	Snowy Cotinga	WF, FE, R	0-500	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Tityridae	Tityras, Becards & Allies					
421	<i>Schiffornis veraepacis</i>	Northern Schiffornis	WF, CF	0-1300	C e (u - r, l), Cb nw (c, l), Cb s (u, l)	R	LC
422	<i>Laniocera rufescens</i>	Speckled Mourner	WF	0-1000	C e (ac, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
423	<i>Tityra semifasciata</i>	Masked Tityra	F, FE, SF	0-1900	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
424	<i>Tityra inquisitor</i>	Black-crowned Tityra	WF, FE, SF	0-1350	P s (ac), C e (r, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
425	<i>Pachyramphus cinnamomeus</i>	Cinnamon Becard	WF, FE, SF	0-1250	C e (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
426	<i>Pachyramphus polychopterus</i>	White-winged Becard	F, FE, SF	0-800	P s (ac), C e (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
427	<i>Pachyramphus major</i>	Gray-collared Becard	CF, FE	1200 +	C e (u, l)	R	LC
428	<i>Pachyramphus aglaiae</i>	Rose-throated Becard	DF, SF, FE, S, EX	0-700; 1300	P (c), C (u), Cb s (u)	R, M	LC
	Onychorhynchidae	Royal Flycatcher & Allies					
429	<i>Onychorhynchus coronatus</i>	Royal Flycatcher	WF, SF, R, CF	0-1200	P s (vr, l), C e (r, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
430	<i>Terenotriccus erythrurus</i>	Ruddy-tailed Flycatcher	WF, CF, FE	0-1100	P s (ac), C e (ac), Cb (c)	R	LC
431	<i>Myiobius sulphureipygius</i>	Sulphur-rumped Flycatcher	WF, CF	0-1300	C e (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Tyrannidae	Flycatchers					
432	<i>Piprites griseiceps</i>	Gray-headed Piprites	WF, FE	0-600	Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
433	<i>Platyrinchus cancrominus</i>	Stub-tailed Spadebill	WF, CF, FE	0-1400	P s (r, l), C e (u, l), Cb (u - c, l)	R	LC
434	<i>Platyrinchus coronatus</i>	Golden-crowned Spadebill	WF, SF	0-800	C e (ac), Cb nw- Cb se (u, l)	R	LC
435	<i>Mionectes oleagineus</i>	Ochre-bellied Flycatcher	F, FE	0-1800	P s v (vr, l), C e (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC

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436	<i>Leptopogon amaurocephalus</i>	Sepia-capped Flycatcher	CF, WF, SF	0-1400	C e (u, l), Cb (r)	R	LC
437	<i>Myiornis atricapillus</i>	Black-capped Pygmy-Tyrant	WF	0-650	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
438	<i>Lophotriccus pileatus</i>	Scale-crested Pygmy-Tyrant	WF, CF	450-1300	C e (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
439	<i>Oncostoma cinereigulare</i>	Northern Bentbill	SF, FE	0-1300	P s v (vr), C e (c,l), Cb (c)	R	LC
440	<i>Poecilatriccus sylvia</i>	Slate-headed Tody-Flycatcher	FE, SF, S	0-1300	P (u,l), C (vr), Cb (c,l)	R	LC
441	<i>Todirostrum cinereum</i>	Common Tody-Flycatcher	FE,SF, EX	0-1450	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
442	<i>Todirostrum nigriceps</i>	Black-headed Tody-Flycatcher	WF, R	0-1150	Cb n (u, l), Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
443	<i>Rhynchocyclus brevirostris</i>	Eye-ringed Flatbill	WF, CF, SF	0-1500	P v (ac, l), C e (u,l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
444	<i>Tolmomyias sulphurescens</i>	Yellow-olive Flycatcher	F	0-1700	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
445	<i>Tolmomyias assimilis</i>	Yellow-margined Flycatcher	WF, R	0-200	Cb s (u, l)	R	LC
446	<i>Ornithion semiflavum</i>	Yellow-bellied Tyrannulet	WF, FE	0-550	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
447	<i>Ornithion brunneicapillus</i>	Brown-capped Tyrannulet	WF, FE	0-50	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
448	<i>Camptostoma imberbe</i>	Northern Beardless-Tyrannulet	DF, S, EX, PS	0-1000	P (c, l), C e (r, l), Cb (r, l)	R	LC
449	<i>Capsiempis flaveola</i>	Yellow Tyrannulet	S, FE, SF	0-600	Cb n (r, l), Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
450	<i>Myiopagis viridicata</i>	Greenish Elaenia	FE, SF, PS, DF	0-1300	P (r - u, l), C (r, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
451	<i>Elaenia flavogaster</i>	Yellow-bellied Elaenia	SF, FE, S, EX, PS	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
452	<i>Elaenia frantzii</i>	Mountain Elaenia	CF, SF	1000 +	P v (c,l), C (c,l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
453	<i>Zimmerius parvus</i>	Mistletoe Tyrannulet	FE, SF, F	0-1200	C (r-u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
454	<i>Attila spadiceus</i>	Bright-rumped Attila	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (u, l), C e (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
455	<i>Rhytipterna holerythra</i>	Rufous Mourner	WF, FE, CF	0-1400	C e (vr, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
456	<i>Myiarchus tuberculifer</i>	Dusky-capped Flycatcher	SF, FE, S, EX, U	0-1600	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC

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457	<i>Myiarchus cinerascens</i>	Ash-throated Flycatcher	DF, S, EX	0-1200	P (r), C w (r)	M	LC
458	<i>Myiarchus nuttingi</i>	Nutting's Flycatcher	DF, S, EX, FE	0-1000	P (c), C w (r)	R	LC
459	<i>Myiarchus crinitus</i>	Great Crested Flycatcher	F, DF, FE	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb (u)	M	LC
460	<i>Myiarchus tyrannulus</i>	Brown-crested Flycatcher	DF, S, EX, PF, Mg	0-1500	P (a), C w (u), Cb s L (ac)	R	LC
461	<i>Pitangus sulphuratus</i>	Great Kiskadee	O, S, EX, FE	0-1500	P (a), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
462	<i>Megarynchus pitangua</i>	Boat-billed Flycatcher	F, FE, SF, PF	0-1600	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
463	<i>Myiozetetes similis</i>	Social Flycatcher	SF, EX, FE, U	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
464	<i>Myiozetetes granadensis</i>	Gray-capped Flycatcher	FE, SF, O	0-1400	C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
465	<i>Conopias albobittatus</i>	White-ringed Flycatcher	WF, FE, R, SF	0-600	C (ac), Cb (u)	R	LC
466	<i>Myiodynastes maculatus</i>	Streaked Flycatcher	F, FE	0-1500	P sw (u - r, l), C (e), Cb L (u)	P/S, R	LC
467	<i>Myiodynastes luteiventris</i>	Sulphur-bellied Flycatcher	F, FE	0-1800	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	S	LC
468	<i>Legatus leucophaeus</i>	Piratic Flycatcher	WF, FE, SF, CF	0-1300	P (r, l), C (u, l), Cb (c)	S	LC
469	<i>Tyrannus melancholicus</i>	Tropical Kingbird	O	0-1600	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
470	<i>Tyrannus vociferans</i>	Cassin's Kingbird	O, EX	600-1400	P (vr, l), C (r, l)	R	LC
471	<i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>	Western Kingbird	EX, FE, SF, O	0-1500	P (c), C w (c), Cb sw (u)	R	LC
472	<i>Tyrannus tyrannus</i>	Eastern Kingbird	FE, SF	0-1500	P (u), C (r), Cb (c)	PM	LC
473	<i>Tyrannus dominicensis</i>	Gray Kingbird	SF, O, S	0-100	Cb e, i (vr)	PM	LC
474	<i>Tyrannus caudifasciatus</i>	N Loggerhead Kingbird	W, O	0	Cb i (ac)	V	LC
475	<i>Tyrannus forficatus</i>	Scissor-tailed Flycatcher	O, S, EX	0-1200	P (a), C (c), Cb sw L (u)	M	LC
476	<i>Tyrannus savana</i>	Fork-tailed Flycatcher	PS, O, EX, S, U	0-1300	P L (ac), C (u), Cb (c - a, l)	R	LC
477	<i>Aphanotriccus capitalis</i>	Tawny-chested Flycatcher	WF, FE, SF, R	0-400	Cb (u, l)	R	VU
478	<i>Mitrephanes phaeocercus</i>	Tufted Flycatcher	CF, FE	1300 +	C n (c, l), C s (vr)	R	LC
479	<i>Contopus cooperi</i>	Olive-sided Flycatcher	F, FE	0-1700	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (u, l)	P, M	NT
480	<i>Contopus pertinax</i>	Greater Pewee	PF, PS, FE	1000-1800; 0-50	C (c, l), Cb ne (r, l)	R	LC

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481	<i>Contopus sordidulus</i>	Western Wood-Pewee	PF, CF, FE, DF	0-1500	P (u), C (u), Cb (vr)	P	LC
482	<i>Contopus virens</i>	Eastern Wood-Pewee	F, FE, SF, O	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	P	LC
483	<i>Contopus cinereus</i>	Tropical Pewee	F, FE, SF, W, R	0-1500	P (u), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
484	<i>Empidonax flaviventris</i>	Yellow-bellied Flycatcher	F, FE, SF	0-1500	P (u), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
485	<i>Empidonax virescens</i>	Acadian Flycatcher	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (r), C (u), Cb (c)	M	LC
486	<i>Empidonax alnorum</i>	Alder Flycatcher	SF, S, EX	0-1300	P (r), C (r), Cb s L (r)	P	LC
487	<i>Empidonax traillii</i>	Willow Flycatcher	SF, S, EX	0-1300	P (u), C (r), Cb s (r)	M	LC
488	<i>Empidonax albigularis</i>	White-throated Flycatcher	SF, S, EX	1000-1500	C (r)	R	LC
489	<i>Empidonax minimus</i>	Least Flycatcher	FE, SF, S, EX	0-1500	P (r), C (u), Cb (vr)	M	LC
490	<i>Empidonax hammondii</i>	Hammond's Flycatcher	PF, CF, FE, SF	800 +	C (r, l)	M	LC
491	<i>Empidonax flavescens</i>	Yellowish Flycatcher	CF, PF, FE, SF	800-1800	C (c, l)	R	LC
492	<i>Empidonax fulvifrons</i>	Buff-breasted Flycatcher	PF	1100 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
493	<i>Sayornis nigricans</i>	Black Phoebe	R	600 +	C (c, l), Cb (r), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
494	<i>Pyrocephalus rubinus</i>	Vermilion Flycatcher	PS	0-100	Cb ne (c, l)	R	LC
495	<i>Colonia colonus</i>	Long-tailed Tyrant	WF, FE, R	0-600	C e (ac), Cb (u)	R	LC
	Thamnophilidae	Antbirds					
496	<i>Cymbilaimus lineatus</i>	Fasciated Antshrike	WF	0-400	C (ac), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
497	<i>Taraba major</i>	Great Antshrike	WF, FE, SF, R	0-600	C (r, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
498	<i>Thamnophilus doliatus</i>	Barred Antshrike	DF, SF, S, EX, PF	0-1200	P (c), C (u -c), Cb (u)	R	LC
499	<i>Thamnophilus atrinucha</i>	Black-crowned Antshrike	WF, FE, SF	0-600	P s L (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
500	<i>Thamnistes anabatinus</i>	Russet Antshrike	WF	0-1000	Cb n (c,l), Cb s (r)	R	LC
501	<i>Dysithamnus mentalis</i>	Plain Antwreio	WF, CF	400-1300	C e (r), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
502	<i>Dysithamnus striaticeps</i>	Streak-crowned Antwreio	WF	0-600	Cb (c,l)	R	LC
503	<i>Myrmotherula axillaris</i>	White-flanked Antwren	WF	0-900	Cb (u, l)	R	LC

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504	<i>Myrmotherula schisticolor</i>	Slaty Antwren	CF, FE	400-1500	C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
505	<i>Epinecrophylla fulviventris</i>	Checker-throated Stipplethroat	WF	0-800	Cb (u- c, l)	R	LC
506	<i>Microrhopias quixensis</i>	Dot-winged Antwren	WF	0-600	C e (ac), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
507	<i>Cercomacroides tyrannina</i>	Dusky Antbird	CF, WF, DF, FE	0-1400	P (c,l), C (u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
508	<i>Gymnocichla nudiceps</i>	Bare-crowned Antbird	WF, FE	0-400	C e (ac), Cb (u)	R	LC
509	<i>Myrmeciza zeledoni</i>	Zeledon's Antbird	WF	0-50	Cb (ac)	R	LC
510	<i>Poliocrania exsul</i>	Chestnut-backed Antbird	WF	0-600	Cb n (r - u), Cb s (c)	R	LC
511	<i>Hylophylax naevioides</i>	Spotted Antbird	WF, FE	0-1000	P s L (r, l), C (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
512	<i>Myrmornis torquata</i>	Wing-banded Antbird	WF	0-1000	Cb n (u, l)	R	LC
513	<i>Gymnopithys bicolor</i>	Bicolored Antbird	WF	0-1000	C (vr, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
514	<i>Phaenostictus mcleannani</i>	Ocellated Antbird	WF	0-1100	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Grallariidae	Antpittas					
515	<i>Grallaria guatemalensis</i>	Scaled Antpitta	CF	1000-1600	C (r, l), Cb (r, l)	R	LC
516	<i>Hylopezus perspicillatus</i>	Streak-chested Antpitta	WF	0-500	Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
517	<i>Hylopezus dives</i>	Thicket Antpitta	WF	0-1000	C e (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
	Formicariidae	Antthrushes					
518	<i>Formicarius analis</i>	Black-faced Antthrush	CF	0-1400	C e (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
	Furnariidae	Ovenbirds & Woodcreepers					
519	<i>Sclerurus mexicanus</i>	Tawny-throated Leaftosser	CF	1200+	C e (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
520	<i>Sclerurus guatemalensis</i>	Scaly-throated Leaftosser	WF	0-1000	Cb n (c,l), Cb s (r)	R	LC
521	<i>Sittasomus griseicapillus</i>	Olivaceous Woodcreeper	WF, CF, DF, FE	0-1400	P s L (ac, l), C e (u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
522	<i>Deconychura longicauda</i>	Long-tailed Woodcreeper	WF	0-1000	Cb n (u, l), Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
523	<i>Dendrocincla homochroa</i>	Ruddy Woodcreeper	WF, CF, DF	0-1450	P s (r, l), C (u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC

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524	<i>Dendrocincla anabatina</i>	Tawny-winged Woodcreeper	CF, WF, SF	0-1350	C e (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
525	<i>Dendrocincla fuliginosa</i>	Plain-brown Woodcreeper	WF, SF	0-800 (1300)	C (vr, l), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
526	<i>Glyphorhynchus spirurus</i>	Wedge-billed Woodcreeper	WF, SF	0-1100	C e (ac), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
527	<i>Dendrocolaptes sanctithomae</i>	Northern Barred-Woodcreeper	WF, CF, DF	0-1400	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
528	<i>Dendrocolaptes picumnus</i>	Black-banded Woodcreeper	CF, PF	1200 +	C (vr - ac?, l)	R	LC
529	<i>Xiphocolaptes promeropirhynchus</i>	Strong-billed Woodcreeper	CF, PF	1000 +	C (u, l), Cb ne (u, l)	R	LC
530	<i>Xiphorhynchus susurrans</i>	Cocoa Woodcreeper	WF	0-1200	C e (vr, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
531	<i>Xiphorhynchus flavigaster</i>	Ivory-billed Woodcreeper	DF, PF, CF	0-1400	P (c, l), C (u, l), Cb s L (r, l)	R	LC
532	<i>Xiphorhynchus lachrymosus</i>	Black-striped Woodcreeper	WF	0-200	Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
533	<i>Xiphorhynchus erythropygius</i>	Spotted Woodcreeper	CF, WF	0-1400	C e (u, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
534	<i>Campylorhamphus pusillus</i>	Brown-billed Scythebill	WF	0-50	Cb s (ac)	R	LC
535	<i>Lepidocolaptes souleyetii</i>	Streak-headed Woodcreeper	F, FE, SF	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
536	<i>Lepidocolaptes affinis</i>	Spot-crowned Woodcreeper	CF	1300 +	C (vr, l)	R	LC
537	<i>Xenops minutus</i>	Plain Xenops	WF, CF, FE	0-1400	P s L (ac- vr, l), C (u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
538	<i>Anabacerthia variegaticeps</i>	Scaly-throated Foliage-gleaner	CF	1200 +	C (vr)	R	LC
539	<i>Clibanornis rubiginosus</i>	Ruddy Foliage-gleaner	WF, PF	1100-1900	C (u, l)	R	LC
540	<i>Automolus ochrolaemus</i>	Buff-throated Foliage-gleaner	CF, WF	0-1400	C e (c, l), Cb (c - r, l)	R	LC
541	<i>Automolus subulatus</i>	Striped Woodhaunter	WF	0-900	C e (ext?), Cb n (u, l), Cb s (vr)	R	LC
542	<i>Synallaxis brachyura</i>	Slaty Spinetail	FE, S, SF, R	0-1300	C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UICN
	Vireonidae	Vireos					
543	<i>Cyclarhis gujanensis</i>	Rufous-browed Peppershrike	DF, SF, FE, Mg, EX	200 +	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
544	<i>Vireolanius pulchellus</i>	Green Shrike-Vireo	WF, CF	0-1800	C e (r, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
545	<i>Tunchiornis ochraceiceps</i>	Tawny-crowned Greenlet	WF, CF	0-1350	C e (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
546	<i>Pachysylvia decurtata</i>	Lesser Greenlet	F, FE, SF	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
547	<i>Vireo griseus</i>	White-eyed Vireo	S, SF	0-?	P (ac), C (ac), Cb (vr)	M	LC
548	<i>Vireo pallens</i>	Mangrove Vireo	Mg, S, SF, FE	0-100	P (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
549	<i>Vireo bellii</i>	Bell's Vireo	?	1000	C (ac)	V	NT
550	<i>Vireo flavifrons</i>	Yellow-throated Vireo	F, FE, SF	0-1700	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
551	<i>Vireo solitarius</i>	Blue-headed Vireo	F, FE, SF	0-1700	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
552	<i>Vireo plumbeus</i>	Plumbeous Vireo	PF	1100 +	C (u, l)	M	LC
553	<i>Vireo philadelphicus</i>	Philadelphia Vireo	DF, CF, FE, SF	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (r)	M	LC
554	<i>Vireo gilvus</i>	Warbling Vireo	EX, PF, SF	0-1550	P (u), C (c) Cb s (r)	M	LC
555	<i>Vireo leucophrys</i>	Brown-capped Vireo	CF, FE, SF	1300 +	C (r - u, l)	R	LC
556	<i>Vireo olivaceus</i>	Red-eyed Vireo	F, FE, SF	0-1700	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	P	LC
557	<i>Vireo flavoviridis</i>	Yellow-green Vireo	DF, SF, FE, R	0-1400	P (a), C (u), Cb (r)	S	LC
	Corvidae	Jays and Crows					
558	<i>Calocitta formosa</i>	White-throated Magpie-Jay	DF, EX, Mg, S, O	0-1400	P (a), C (u), Cb sw L (u)	R	LC
559	<i>Psilorhinus morio</i>	Brown Jay	SF, S	0-1700	C e (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
560	<i>Cyanocorax yncas</i>	Green Jay	PS	0-50	Cb ne (ac)	V	LC
561	<i>Cyanocorax melanocyaneus</i>	Bushy-crested Jay	FE, PF, SF	900 +	C (c - a, l)	R	LC
562	<i>Cyanocitta stelleri</i>	Steller's Jay	PF	1200 +	C n (c, l)	R	LC

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563	<i>Aphelocoma unicolor</i>	Unicolored Jay	CF, PF	1200 +	C n (u, l)	R	LC
564	<i>Corvus corax</i>	Common Raven	DF, EX, PF	1200 +	P (ac), C (u, l), Cb w (ac)	R	LC
	Hirundinidae	Swallows					
565	<i>Riparia riparia</i>	Bank Swallow	R, W	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (u)	M, P	LC
566	<i>Tachycineta bicolor</i>	Tree Swallow	O, S	0-1250	P (r), C (r), Cb (r)	M	LC
567	<i>Tachycineta thalassina</i>	Violet-green Swallow	PF, FE, O	0-1300	P (vr), C (u)	M	LC
568	<i>Tachycineta albilinea</i>	Mangrove Swallow	W, R	0-1000	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
569	<i>Pygochelidon cyanoleuca</i>	Blue-and-white Swallow	?	0-200	P s (vr - ac?)	V/S	LC
570	<i>Stelgidopteryx serripennis</i>	Northern Rough-winged Swallow	W, O	0-1600	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	M, R	LC
571	<i>Stelgidopteryx ruficollis</i>	Southern Rough-winged Swallow	O, W	0-1300	P s (u), C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
572	<i>Progne subis</i>	Purple Martin	O, W	0-1400	P (r), C (vr), Cb (u)	P	LC
573	<i>Progne chalybea</i>	Gray-breasted Martin	O	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
574	<i>Progne sinaloae</i>	^N Sinaloa Martin	W	100	Cb sw (ac)	V/MP?	VU
575	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn Swallow	O	0-1400	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	M	LC
576	<i>Petrochelidon pyrrhonota</i>	Cliff Swallow	O, W	0-1500	P (a), C (u), Cb n (u), Cb s (c)	M, P	LC
577	<i>Petrochelidon fulva</i>	Cave Swallow	W, O	0-200 - ?	P (r), Cb s L (r)	M	LC
	Bombycillidae	Waxwings					
578	<i>Bombycilla cedrorum</i>	Cedar Waxwing	PF, CF, SF	650 +	P (vr), C (r), Cb (ac)	M	LC
	Certhiidae	Treecreepers					
579	<i>Certhia americana</i>	Brown Creeper	PF	1000 +	C n (u, l), C (vr, l)	R	LC
	Poliioptilidae	Gnatwrens & Gnatcatchers					
580	<i>Ramphocaenus melanurus</i>	Long-billed Gnatwren	WF, FE, SF	0-1400	P (u, l), C e (r-u, l), Cb (u)	R	LC

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581	<i>Microbates cinereiventris</i>	Tawny-faced Gnatwren	WF	0-400	Cb (r, l)	R	LC
582	<i>Polioptila bilineata</i>	White-browed Gnatcatcher	WF, SF, R	0-1350	P (r, l), C e (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
583	<i>Polioptila caerulea</i>	Blue-gray Gnatcatcher	PF, FE	100-1400	P (vr), C (r, l), Cb (r, l)	M	LC
584	<i>Polioptila albiloris</i>	White-lored Gnatcatcher	DF, EX, S, SF	0-1400	P (c), C w (u), Cb sw L (vr)	R	LC
	Troglodytidae	Wrens					
585	<i>Salpinctes obsoletus</i>	Rock Wren	EX, S, O	700+	P n v (u, l), C w (c, l)	R	LC
586	<i>Microcerculus philomela</i>	Nightingale Wren	WF, CF	300-1400	C e (u, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
587	<i>Troglodytes aedon</i>	House Wren	SF, FE, EX	0-1700	P (r - u, l), C (a), Cb (c)	R	LC
588	<i>Troglodytes rufociliatus</i>	Rufous-browed Wren	CF, PF	1200 +	C n (u, l), C s (vr)	R	LC
589	<i>Cistothorus platensis</i>	Grass Wren	FG	0-1000	C (vr), Cb (u, l)	R	LC
590	<i>Thryothorus ludovicianus</i>	Carolina Wren	EX, S, DF	450-1300	P n v (u, l), C w (u, l)	R	LC
591	<i>Campylorhynchus zonatus</i>	Band-backed Wren	PF, SF	600 +	C (c - a, l), Cb s (ac)	R	LC
592	<i>Campylorhynchus rufinucha</i>	Rufous-naped Wren	EX, S, SF, O, Mg, U	0-1400	P (a), C (u), Cb sw L (r)	R	LC
593	<i>Pheugopedius atrogularis</i>	Black-throated Wren	WF, FE, SF	0-100	Cb n (ac), Cb s (c)	R	LC
594	<i>Pheugopedius maculipectus</i>	Spot-breasted Wren	FE, SF	0-1400	C e (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
595	<i>Thryophilus rufalbus</i>	Rufous-and-white Wren	DF, SF, FE, S	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb w (r,l)	R	LC
596	<i>Thryophilus pleurostictus</i>	Banded Wren	EX, DF, FE	0-1300	P (c), C (r - u), Cb w (ac)	R	LC
597	<i>Cantorchilus thoracicus</i>	Stripe-breasted Wren	WF	0-800	C e (vr, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
598	<i>Cantorchilus modestus</i>	Cabanis's Wren	F, FE, SF	0-2000	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
599	<i>Cantorchilus zeledoni</i>	Canebreak Wren	FG, R	0-100	Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
600	<i>Cantorchilus nigricapillus</i>	Bay Wren	FE, WF, SF	0-700	Cb s (c, l), Cb n (vr)	R	LC
601	<i>Henicorhina leucosticta</i>	White-breasted Wood-Wren	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1400	C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
602	<i>Henicorhina leucophrys</i>	Gray-breasted Wood-Wren	CF	1300 +	C (hypothetical)	R	LC

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603	<i>Cyphorhinus phaeocephalus</i>		Song Wren	WF	0-800	Cb (vr - u, l)	R	LC
	Mimidae		Mockingbirds					
604	<i>Melanotis hypoleucus</i>		Blue-and-white Mockingbird	SF, S, EX, PF	1200 +	C o (vr, l)	R	LC
605	<i>Dumetella carolinensis</i>		Gray Catbird	S, SF	0-1500	P (r), C (u), Cb (c)	M, P	LC
606	<i>Mimus gilvus</i>		Tropical Mockingbird	O, S, EX, U	0-1400	P (c), C w (c, l)	R	LC
607	<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>	N	Northern Mockingbird	O	0-100 ?	P (ac)	V	LC
	Cinclidae		Dippers					
608	<i>Cinclus mexicanus</i>		American Dipper	R, F	300 +	C (ext?), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
	Turdidae		Thrushes & Allies					
609	<i>Sialia sialis</i>		Eastern Bluebird	PF, PS	1000+; 0-50	C (c, l), Cb ne (c, l)	R	LC
610	<i>Myadestes unicolor</i>		Slate-colored Solitaire	CF	1000 +	C (c, l), Cb nw (c, l)	R	LC
611	<i>Catharus aurantiirostris</i>		Orange-billed Nightingale-Thrush	CF, FE, PF, SF	300 +	P (c,l), C (c), Cb nw L (r)	R	LC
612	<i>Catharus frantzii</i>		Ruddy-capped Nightingale-Thrush	CF, PF	1200 +	C (r-u, l), Cb nw (c,l)	R	LC
613	<i>Catharus mexicanus</i>		Black-headed Nightingale-Thrush	CF	600 +; 1000 +	P s v (u,l), C (c, l)	R	LC
614	<i>Catharus dryas</i>		Yellow-throated Nightingale-Thrush	CF	1400 +	C w (u, l)	R	LC
615	<i>Catharus fuscescens</i>		Veery	WF, FE, SF	0-1200	C e (r-u), Cb (r-u)	P	LC
616	<i>Catharus minimus</i>		Gray-cheeked Thrush	FE, SF, S	0-1300	P (u), C (u), Cb (u)	P	LC
617	<i>Catharus ustulatus</i>		Swainson's Thrush	F, FE	0-1800	P (c), C (c-a), Cb (c)	M	LC
618	<i>Hylocichla mustelina</i>		Wood Thrush	F, FE, SF	0-1800	P (r-u), C (c-a), Cb (c-a)	M	LC
619	<i>Turdus infuscatus</i>		Black Thrush	CF, PF, FE	1200 +	C n (r, l)	R	LC

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620	<i>Turdus plebejus</i>		Mountain Thrush	F	1200 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
621	<i>Turdus grayi</i>		Clay-colored Thrush	SF, DF, EX, O	0-1600	P (a), C (a), Cb (a)	R	LC
622	<i>Turdus assimilis</i>		White-throated Thrush	CF, WF, FE	500 +	P i v (u, l), C (u, l), Cb (c, l)	R	LC
623	<i>Turdus rufopalliatus</i>	N	Rufous-backed Robin	DF, S	700	C (ac)	V	LC
	Peucedramidae		Olive Warbler					
624	<i>Peucedramus taeniatus</i>		Olive Warbler	PF	1200-1800	C n (u, l), C s (vr)	R	LC
	Estrildidae		Waxbills & Munias					
625	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>		Tricolored Munia	O	0-100	P (u, l)	R	LC
	Passeridae		Old World Sparrows					
626	<i>Passer domesticus</i>		House Sparrow	U, O	0-1300	P (a, l), C (a, l), Cb (a, l)	R	LC
	Fringillidae		Euphonias & Chlorophonias					
627	<i>Chlorophonia elegantissima</i>		Elegant Euphonia	CF, PF, FE, SF	1050 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
628	<i>Chlorophonia occipitalis</i>		Blue-crowned Chlorophonia	CF, FE, SF	1000 +	C (u-c, l)	R	LC
629	<i>Chlorophonia callophrys</i>		Golden-browed Chlorophonia	WF, FE, CF	1000 +; 100	Cb sw L (ac), C (ac)	V	LC
630	<i>Euphonia affinis</i>		Scrub Euphonia	DF, SF, EX, S	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb sw (u)	R	LC
631	<i>Euphonia luteicapilla</i>		Yellow-crowned Euphonia	FE, SF	0-1300	P s L (vr), C u (u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
632	<i>Euphonia minuta</i>		White-vented Euphonia	WF	0-1000	Cb (r-u, l)	R	LC
633	<i>Euphonia hirundinacea</i>		Yellow-throated Euphonia	F, FE, SF	0-1500	P (u-c, l), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
634	<i>Euphonia gouldi</i>		Olive-backed Euphonia	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1300	C e (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
635	<i>Loxia curvirostra</i>		Red Crossbill	PF, PS	1200 +; 0-50	C (u, l), Cb ne (u, l)	R	LC
636	<i>Spinus notatus</i>		Black-headed Siskin	PF, PS	1200 +; 0-50	C (c-a, l), Cb ne (u, l)	R	LC
637	<i>Spinus psaltria</i>		Lesser Goldfinch	PF	600 +	P n v (r, l), C (c-u, l)	R	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UICN
	Passerellidae	New World Sparrows					
638	<i>Chlorospingus flavopectus</i>	Common Chlorospingus	CF, FE	700 +	C e (a, l), Cb n (a, l)	R	LC
639	<i>Peucaea ruficauda</i>	Stripe-headed Sparrow	DF, EX, S, O	0-1500	P (c), C w (c), Cb w L (ac)	R	LC
640	<i>Peucaea botterii</i>	Botteri's Sparrow	PS	0-100	Cb ne (c, l)	R	LC
641	<i>Ammodramus savannarum</i>	Grasshopper Sparrow	S, EX, PS, FG	0-1400	P (r, l), C w (r, l); Cb n (u, l)	M, R	LC
642	<i>Arremonops rufivirgatus</i>	Olive Sparrow	DF, R, SF	0-800	P (u, l)	R	LC
643	<i>Arremonops conirostris</i>	Black-striped Sparrow	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1400	P L (ac), C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
644	<i>Chondestes grammacus</i>	N Lark Sparrow	S	0-100	P (ac)	V	LC
645	<i>Spizella passerina</i>	Chipping Sparrow	PF, PS	1100-1600; 0-50	C (c, l), Cb ne (a, l)	R	LC
646	<i>Arremon aurantirostris</i>	Orange-billed Sparrow	WF, FE, SF	0-800	C e (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
647	<i>Arremon brunneinucha</i>	Chestnut-capped Brushfinch	CF, FE	550-1800	P s v (r, l), C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
648	<i>Zonotrichia capensis</i>	Rufous-collared Sparrow	EX, S, O	1000 +	C (vr)	R	LC
649	<i>Passerculus sandwichensis</i>	Savannah Sparrow	O, W	0-450	P (ac, l), C sw (ac, l)	V	LC
650	<i>Melospiza lincolnii</i>	N Lincoln's Sparrow	S	1000-?	C (ac)	V	LC
651	<i>Melozone leucotis</i>	White-eared Ground-Sparrow	FE, SF	1100 +	C (u, l)	R	LC
652	<i>Aimophila rufescens</i>	Rusty Sparrow	PF, PS, S, EX	800-1600	C (c), Cb ne (u, l), Cb sw (ac)	R	LC
653	<i>Atlapetes albinucha</i>	White-naped Brushfinch	PF, FE, CF, SF	800 +	C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
	Icteriidae	Yellow-breasted Chat					
654	<i>Icteria virens</i>	Yellow-breasted Chat	FE, S	0-1300	P (r-u), C (r-u), Cb (r-u)	M	LC
	Icteridae	Blackbirds & Orioles					
655	<i>Xanthocephalus xanthocephalus</i>	Yellow-headed Blackbird	O, FG	0-1000	C (ac), Cb s L (ac)	V	LC
656	<i>Dolichonyx oryzivorus</i>	Bobolink	O, FG	0-50	Cb e (r)	P	LC

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657	<i>Sturnella magna</i>	Eastern Meadowlark	O	0-1600	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	R	NT
658	<i>Leistes militaris</i>	Red-breasted Meadowlark	O, FG	0-100	P (r), Cb s (r)	R	LC
659	<i>Amblycercus holosericeus</i>	Yellow-billed Cacique	DF, FE, SF	0-1400	P (u, l), C (u), Cb (c)	R	LC
660	<i>Psarocolius wagleri</i>	Chestnut-headed Oropendola	WF, CF, FE, SF	0-1600	C e (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
661	<i>Psarocolius montezuma</i>	Montezuma Oropendola	F, FE, SF	0-1400	P (u-c, l), C e (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
662	<i>Cacicus uropygialis</i>	Scarlet-rumped Cacique	WF, FE	0-700	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
663	<i>Icterus wagleri</i>	Black-vented Oriole	PF, FE, EX, S	1000 +	C (r-u, l)	R	LC
664	<i>Icterus prothemelas</i>	Black-cowled Oriole	FE, SF	0-1300	C e (u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
665	<i>Icterus spurius</i>	Orchard Oriole	SF, DF, R, W	0-1400	P (c), C (u), Cb (c)	M	LC
666	<i>Icterus chrysater</i>	Yellow-backed Oriole	PF, FE, PS	600 +; 0-50	P n v (r, l), C (c, l), Cb ne (u, l)	R	LC
667	<i>Icterus mesomelas</i>	Yellow-tailed Oriole	R, FG, FE	0-400	Cb n (u), Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
668	<i>Icterus pustulatus</i>	Streak-backed Oriole	DF, FE, EX, U	0-1600	P (c), C w (c, l)	R	LC
669	<i>Icterus pectoralis</i>	Spot-breasted Oriole	DF, FE, EX, U	0-1600	P (a), C w (c), Cb w (r)	R	LC
670	<i>Icterus gularis</i>	Altamira Oriole	EX, S, SF	0-1400	P (u), C nw (c)	R	LC
671	<i>Icterus galbula</i>	Baltimore Oriole	FE, SF, R, U	0-1500	P (c-a), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
672	<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>	Red-winged Blackbird	FG, W	0-450	P (c-a, l), C sw (c, l)	R	LC
673	<i>Molothrus aeneus</i>	Bronzed Cowbird	O, U	0-1600	P (c-a), C (c), Cb (u)	R	LC
674	<i>Molothrus oryzivorus</i>	Giant Cowbird	FE, SF, R	0-1400	P (r), C (u), Cb (u)	R	LC
675	<i>Dives dives</i>	Melodious Blackbird	FE, O, U	0-1600	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
676	<i>Quiscalus mexicanus</i>	Great-tailed Grackle	O, FG, U	0-1550	P (a), C (a), Cb (c)	R	LC
677	<i>Quiscalus nicaraguensis</i>	Nicaraguan Grackle	W, FG, R	0-100	P L (u, l), Cb sw (r, l)	R	LC
	Parulidae	New World Warblers					
678	<i>Seiurus aurocapilla</i>	Ovenbird	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	M	LC
679	<i>Helmitheros vermivorum</i>	Worm-eating Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1300	P (r-u, l), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	M	LC

	Species		Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UICN
680	<i>Parkesia motacilla</i>		Louisiana Waterthrush	R, F	0-1350	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	M	LC
681	<i>Parkesia noveboracensis</i>		Northern Waterthrush	W	0-1500	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	M	LC
682	<i>Vermivora chrysoptera</i>		Golden-winged Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1500	P s (r, l), C (c, l), Cb (u, l)	M	NT
683	<i>Vermivora cyanoptera</i>		Blue-winged Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1400	P (r, l), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	M	LC
684	<i>Mniotilta varia</i>		Black-and-white Warbler	F, FE, SF, Mg, EX	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
685	<i>Protonotaria citrea</i>		Prothonotary Warbler	R, Mg, W, FE	0-1500	P (u, l), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	M	LC
686	<i>Limnothlypis swainsonii</i>	N	Swainson's Warbler	WF, SF	0-100	Cb (ac)	V	LC
687	<i>Oreothlypis superciliosa</i>		Crescent-chested Warbler	PF, CF	1000 +	C (r-u, l)	R	LC
688	<i>Leiothlypis peregrina</i>		Tennessee Warbler	F, SF	0-1600	P (a), C (c) Cb (c)	M	LC
689	<i>Leiothlypis celata</i>	N	Orange-crowned Warbler	FE, SF	100-1300?	C (ac), Cb (ac)	V	LC
690	<i>Leiothlypis ruficapilla</i>		Nashville Warbler	PF, SF, FE	1200?	C (ac)	V	LC
691	<i>Oporornis agilis</i>		Connecticut Warbler	SF, S	1400	C (ac)	V	LC
692	<i>Geothlypis poliocephala</i>		Gray-crowned Yellowthroat	PF, PS, O	0-1650	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
693	<i>Geothlypis tolmiei</i>		MacGillivray's Warbler	FE, SF	700 +	P (r), C (u-c)	M	LC
694	<i>Geothlypis philadelphia</i>		Mourning Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1300	P (r), C (r), Cb (r)	M	LC
695	<i>Geothlypis formosa</i>		Kentucky Warbler	F, FE	0-1400	P (vr, l), C w (r), C e (c, l), Cb (u)	M	LC
696	<i>Geothlypis semiflava</i>		Olive-crowned Yellowthroat	FG, R, W	100?; 0-100	C (ac), Cb n (vr), Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
697	<i>Geothlypis trichas</i>		Common Yellowthroat	W, FG	0-1400	P (e), C w (u)-C e (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
698	<i>Setophaga citrina</i>		Hooded Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1400	P (r, l), C e (u, l), Cb (u)	M	LC
699	<i>Setophaga ruticilla</i>		American Redstart	F, FE, SF	0-1800	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
700	<i>Setophaga tigrina</i>		Cape May Warbler	S, FE, SF	0-?	P (r), Cb (r)	M	LC
701	<i>Setophaga cerulea</i>		Cerulean Warbler	F, FE	0-1500	P (r, l), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	P	NT
702	<i>Setophaga americana</i>		Northern Parula	F, FE, SF	0-1300	P (r), C (r), Cb (r)	M	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UICN
703	<i>Setophaga pitiayumi</i>	Tropical Parula	F, FE, SF	0-100; 500-1600	P s L (vr, l), C (c, l), Cb (r)	R	LC
704	<i>Setophaga magnolia</i>	Magnolia Warbler	FE, SF	0-1400	P (u-c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
705	<i>Setophaga castanea</i>	Bay-breasted Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1400	P (r, l), C (c, l), Cb (c, l)	P	LC
706	<i>Setophaga fusca</i>	Blackburnian Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (r), C (c, l), Cb (r), Cb nw (c, l)	P	LC
707	<i>Setophaga petechia</i>	Yellow Warbler	SF, Mg, S, EX	0-1600	P (a), C w (a), C e (u), Cb (c)	M, R	LC
708	<i>Setophaga pensylvanica</i>	Chestnut-sided Warbler	FE, SF, S	0-1500	P (u-c, l), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
709	<i>Setophaga striata</i>	Blackpoll Warbler	WF, FE, SF	0-100	Cb (ac)	P	LC
710	<i>Setophaga caerulescens</i>	Black-throated Blue Warbler	F, FE	0-1300	P (ac), C (vr, l), Cb (r)	M	LC
711	<i>Setophaga palmarum</i>	Palm Warbler	PS, O, FG	0-100	C (ac), Cb (u)	M	LC
712	<i>Setophaga coronata</i>	Yellow-rumped Warbler	FE, SF, O	0-1400	P (r-u, l), C (u, l), Cb (u, l)	M	LC
713	<i>Setophaga dominica</i>	Yellow-throated Warbler	PF, PS, CF, FE	0-1600	P (ac), C (c, l), Cb ne (c, l), Cb (r)	P, M	LC
714	<i>Setophaga discolor</i>	Prairie Warbler	PS, Mg, O	0-50	Cb (vr)	M	LC
715	<i>Setophaga graciae</i>	Grace's Warbler	PF, CF, PS	600+; 1000+; 0-50	P n v (u, l), C (c, l), Cb ne (c, l)	R	LC
716	<i>Setophaga townsendi</i>	Townsend's Warbler	PF, CF, FE	1000 +	P n v (r-u, l), C (u-c, l)	M	LC
717	<i>Setophaga occidentalis</i>	Hermit Warbler	PF, CF, FE	600 +; 1000 +	P n v (r, l), C (u, l)	M	LC
718	<i>Setophaga chrysoparia</i>	Golden-cheeked Warbler	PF, CF, FE	1200 +	C (u, l)	M	EN
719	<i>Setophaga virens</i>	Black-throated Green Warbler	PF, CF, FE	0-1600	P (r-u, l), C (c, l)	M	LC
720	<i>Myiothlypis fulvicauda</i>	Buff-rumped Warbler	R, F, FE	0-1300	C e (r, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
721	<i>Basileuterus lachrymosus</i>	Fan-tailed Warbler	FE, SF, FE	0-1400	P (u-c, l), C (u, l)	R	LC
722	<i>Basileuterus delatirii</i>	Chestnut-capped Warbler	DF, FE, SF	0-1600	P (c), C (c), Cb w (r)	R	LC
723	<i>Basileuterus culicivorus</i>	Golden-crowned Warbler	CF	800 +	C e (a, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	IUCN
724	<i>Cardellina canadensis</i>	Canada Warbler	F, FE	0-1500	P (r), C (c), Cb (c)	P	LC
725	<i>Cardellina pusilla</i>	Wilson's Warbler	F, FE, SF	0-1800	P (u, l), C (a), Cb (r)	M	LC
726	<i>Myioborus pictus</i>	Painted Redstart	PF	1000-1600	C (c, l)	R	LC
727	<i>Myioborus miniatus</i>	Slate-throated Redstart	PF, CF	900; 1300 +	P n v (vr, l), C (r-u, l), Cb n (u, l)	R	LC
	Cardinalidae	Grosbeaks, Buntings & Allies					
728	<i>Piranga flava</i>	Hepatic Tanager	PF, CF, PS	800-1900; 0-100	P n v (vr, l), C (c, l), Cb n (c, l)	R	LC
729	<i>Piranga rubra</i>	Summer Tanager	F, FE, SF	0-1900	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	M	LC
730	<i>Piranga olivacea</i>	Scarlet Tanager	F, FE	0-1900	P n (vr), P s (u, l), C (u), Cb (c)	P	LC
731	<i>Piranga ludoviciana</i>	Western Tanager	DF, SF, EX, S	0-1400	P (u-c), C (c, l),	M	LC
732	<i>Piranga bidentata</i>	Flame-colored Tanager	PF	1000-1800	C (u, l)	R	LC
733	<i>Piranga leucoptera</i>	White-winged Tanager	CF, FE, PF	1100 +	C (u, l), Cb n (r, l)	R	LC
734	<i>Habia rubica</i>	Red-crowned Ant-Tanager	F, FE, SF	0-1550	P s (r-u, l), C (c), Cb (r)	R	LC
735	<i>Habia fuscicauda</i>	Red-throated Ant-Tanager	F, FE, SF	0-1550	P (r, l), C (u, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
736	<i>Chlorothraupis carmioli</i>	Carmioli's Tanager	WF, R	0-1100	Cb (u- c, l)	R	LC
737	<i>Caryothraustes poliogaster</i>	Black-faced Grosbeak	WF, FE	0-1200	C e (r, l), Cb (u; a, l)	R	LC
738	<i>Pheucticus ludovicianus</i>	Rose-breasted Grosbeak	DF, FE, SF, EX	0-1500	P (c), C (u-c), Cb (r; u, l)	M	LC
739	<i>Amaurospiza concolor</i>	Blue Seedeater	F, Bm	400 +	C (vr, l), Cb (vr, l)	R	LC
740	<i>Cyanoloxia cyanooides</i>	Blue-black Grosbeak	WF, FE	0-1300	C (vr, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
741	<i>Cyanocompsa parellina</i>	Blue Bunting	FE, FE, S	0-50; 1000 +	P nw (u, l), C (u, l)	R	LC
742	<i>Passerina caerulea</i>	Blue Grosbeak	DF, EX, S, SF	0-1500	P (c), C (c), Cb (r)	R, M	LC
743	<i>Passerina cyanea</i>	Indigo Bunting	O, EX, S	0-1400	P (c-a), C (c), Cb (u)	M	LC
744	<i>Passerina ciris</i>	Painted Bunting	O, SF, EX, S	0-1400	P (c-a), C (c), Cb (u)	M	LC

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UCN
745	<i>Spiza americana</i>	Dickcissel	O, SF, EX, S, FG	0-1400	P (a), C (u)	M, PM	LC
	Mitrospingidae	Mitrospingid Tanagers					
746	<i>Mitrospingus cassinii</i>	Dusky-faced Tanager	R, WF	0-50	Cb s (vr, l)	R	LC
	Thraupidae	Tanagers					
747	<i>Thraupis episcopus</i>	Blue-gray Tanager	SF, O, EX, S,U	0-1600	P (c-a), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
748	<i>Thraupis abbas</i>	Yellow-winged Tanager	SF, FE, R	0-1600	C (c), Cb n (c) Cb s (r-u)	R	LC
749	<i>Thraupis palmarum</i>	Palm Tanager	O, R, SF	0-400	P s (r, l), Cb s (c)	R	LC
750	<i>Stilpnia larvata</i>	Golden-hooded Tanager	SF, FE	0-1400	C e (u-c), Cb w (u), Cb e (c)	R	LC
751	<i>Tangara inornata</i>	Plain-colored Tanager	WF, FE, R	0-100	Cb s (vr)	R	LC
752	<i>Tangara lavinia</i>	Rufous-winged Tanager	CF, FE, SF	600-1400	C e (c, l), Cb n (r)	R	LC
753	<i>Tangara gyrola</i>	Bay-headed Tanager	CF, FE	1200 +	C e (vr, l), Cb w (vr, l)	R	LC
754	<i>Sicalis luteola</i>	Grassland Yellow-Finch	PS, O, FG	1000; 0-50	C (vr, l), Cb n (r, l)	R	LC
755	<i>Haplospiza rustica</i>	Slaty Finch	F, Bm	1300 +	P s v (vr, l), C (r, l)	R	LC
756	<i>Diglossa baritula</i>	Cinnamon-bellied Flowerpiercer	PF, CF, FE	1300 +	C (r, l)	R	LC
757	<i>Chlorophanes spiza</i>	Green Honeycreeper	WF, FE, SF, R	0-1300	C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
758	<i>Volatinia jacarina</i>	Blue-black Grassquit	O, W, U	0-1400	P (a), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
759	<i>Eucometis penicillata</i>	Gray-headed Tanager	F, FE	100-1350	P s (c, l), C e (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
760	<i>Loriotus luctuosus</i>	White-shouldered Tanager	WF, FE, SF, R	0-700	C e (ac), Cb (u-r)	R	LC
761	<i>Tachyphonus delatrii</i>	Tawny-crested Tanager	WF, FE, SF	0-800	Cb nw (c, l), Cb (r)	R	LC
762	<i>Tachyphonus rufus</i>	White-lined Tanager	SF, FE, S	0-200	Cb sw (vr), Cb se (u)	R	LC
763	<i>Lanio leucothorax</i>	White-throated Shrike-Tanager	WF	0-100	C e (ext?), Cb n (u, l), Cb s (vr)	R	NT

	Species	Common name	Habitat	Altitudinal Range	Distribution & Abundance	Status	UCN
764	<i>Ramphocelus sanguinolentus</i>	Crimson-collared Tanager	FE, SF	0-1500	C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
765	<i>Ramphocelus passerinii</i>	Scarlet-rumped Tanager	SF	0-1500	C e (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
766	<i>Cyanerpes lucidus</i>	Shining Honeycreeper	WF, FE, SF	0-1300	C e (r-u), Cb nw (c, l), Cb (u)	R	LC
767	<i>Cyanerpes cyaneus</i>	Red-legged Honeycreeper	FE, DF, SF	0-1300	P v (u, l), C (r-u), Cb (c)	R	LC
768	<i>Dacnis venusta</i>	Scarlet-thighed Dacnis	F, FE, SF, R	0-700	Cb nw (r, l), Cb se (r, l)	R	LC
769	<i>Dacnis cayana</i>	Blue Dacnis	WF, FE, R	0-700	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
770	<i>Coereba flaveola</i>	Bananaquit	F, FE, SF	0-1300	C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
771	<i>Tiaris olivaceus</i>	Yellow-faced Grassquit	O, SF, PF, PS	0-1300	P s (u, l), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
772	<i>Sporophila funerea</i>	Thick-billed Seed-Finch	FG, S, SF	0-1300	C e (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
773	<i>Sporophila nuttingi</i>	Nicaraguan Seed-Finch	FG	0-200	Cb n (vr), Cb s (c, l)	R	LC
774	<i>Sporophila corvina</i>	Variable Seedeater	O, SF	0-1600	P (vr), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC
775	<i>Sporophila schistacea</i>	Slate-colored Seedeater	R, Bm	0-200	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
776	<i>Sporophila moreletii</i>	Morelet's Seedeater	O	0-1500	P (c), C (u-c), Cb (c)	R	LC
777	<i>Sporophila nigricollis</i>	Yellow-bellied Seedeater	O, W	100; 1350	C e (ac), Cb sw (vr)	V	LC
778	<i>Sporophila minuta</i>	Ruddy-breasted Seedeater	FG, W	0-500	P (c, l), C sw (c, l), Cb sw (c), Cb (ac)	R	LC
779	<i>Saltator atriceps</i>	Black-headed Saltator	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (c, l), C (c, l), Cb (c)	R	LC
780	<i>Saltator maximus</i>	Buff-throated Saltator	F, FE, SF	0-1600	P (u, l), C (c, l), Cb sw (r), Cb (c)	R	LC
781	<i>Saltator grossus</i>	Slate-colored Grosbeak	WF	0-1000	Cb (u, l)	R	LC
782	<i>Saltator coerulescens</i>	Grayish Saltator	DF, EX, S	0-1400	P (c), C (c), Cb (c)	R	LC

NEW RECORDS

19 new species were recorded since the 2018 publication of the Checklist contained on p. 421 of the *Birds of Nicaragua a Field Guide* and are listed in the table below.

The new records appear in ebird and have passed the corresponding review process. Records documented with photos and videos are marked with an X in the right column of the table below.

The numbers in the left column correspond to the species enumeration in the table Checklist of the Birds of Nicaragua. They are included so that the user can find the corresponding information in the main table.

The new records are presented below. 12 of the 19 new records had been described in the appendix *Hypothetical Species* p. 413 of *Birds of Nicaragua a Field Guide* which means that they were expected species.

	Species	Common Name	Photo
	Podicipedidae	Grebes	
37	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Eared Grebe	X
	Columbidae	Pigeons & Doves	
51	<i>Paraclaravis mondetoura</i>	Maroon-chested Ground Dove	
	Rallidae	Rails	
147	<i>Laterallus jamaicensis</i>	Black Rail	
	Scolopacidae	Sandpipers	
169	<i>Limosa haemastica</i>	Hudsonian Godwit	X
172	<i>Arenaria melanocephala</i>	Black Turnstone	X
175	<i>Calidris pugnax</i>	Ruff	X
	Laridae	Gulls & Terns	
203	<i>Chroicocephalus philadelphia</i>	Bonaparte's Gull	X
	Procellariidae	Shearwaters & Petrels	
239	<i>Puffinus lherminieri</i>	Audubon's Shearwater	
	Phalacrocoracidae	Cormorants	
249	<i>Nannopterum auritum</i>	Double-crested Cormorant	X

	Threskiornithidae	Ibises	
274	<i>Plegadis chihi</i>	White-faced Ibis	X
	Strigidae	Owls	
333	<i>Asio flammeus</i>	Short-eared Owl	X
	Tyrannidae	Tyrant Flycatchers	
474	<i>Tyrannus caudifasciatus</i>	Loggerhead Kingbird	
	Hirundinidae	Swallows	
574	<i>Progne sinaloae</i>	Sinaloa Martin	
	Mimidae	Mockingbirds	
607	<i>Mimus polyglottos</i>	Northern Mockingbird	X
	Turdidae	Thrushes	
623	<i>Turdus rufopalliatus</i>	Rufous-backed Robin	X
	Passerellidae	New World Sparrows	
644	<i>Chondestes grammacus</i>	Lark Sparrow	X
650	<i>Melospiza lincolni</i>	Lincoln's Sparrow	X
	Parulidae	Warblers	
686	<i>Limnothlypis swainsonii</i>	Swainson's Warbler	X
689	<i>Leiothlypis celata</i>	Orange-crowned Warbler	

Eared Grebe *Podiceps nigricollis*

24 March, 2018. Location: Moyúa. Ramsar Site Playitas - Moyúa - Tecomapa, Matagalpa.

Two individuals were sighted and photographed. One in breeding plumage and the other in non-breeding plumage.

The species has a very wide distribution in several continents. In the Americas it has its breeding grounds in southwestern Canada and northwestern United States, its wintering grounds cover the Pacific coast and southern part of the United States, as well as all of Mexico. However, numerous reports of vagrants have been recorded in southern Guatemala, El Salvador, one in Costa Rica and now in Nicaragua. Accidental winter resident in the country.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observer and photographer: Manfred Bienert.

Maroon-chested Ground Dove

Paraclaravis mondetoura

12 and 13 May 2018. Location: Cerro Mogotón above 2000 m. Natural Reserve Dipilto - Jalapa. Nueva Segovia.

Heard from a distance at an altitude of 2000 m. Song composed of 2 notes, the second one being louder, higher and longer. Emission of vocalization every second. huwUUP huwUUP huwUUP huwUUP huwUUP huwUUP huwUUP....

This enigmatic species is rare throughout its range; its distribution and abundance are correlated with infrequent bamboo seeding; therefore, the bird seems to disappear for years when seeds are not available. Its range is from southern Mexico to the extreme southwest of Panama. Always above 1000 or 1200 m.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observers: Liliana Chavarría - Duriaux, Georges Duriaux, Moisés Siles and Wilmer Talavera.

Black Rail *Laterallus jamaicensis*

25 March, 2018. Location: Lávira River. Alamikamba Natural Reserve. Caribe Norte.

One individual responded to the playback in large flooded dense pastures. The sound emitted was the typical song of the species. Species **EN**.

The distribution in the winter territories of the species is poorly known, however, it is known to be a winter resident in Florida and the West Indies. ebird records are found in Belize and Honduras on the north bank of the Río Coco very close to the Nicaraguan border.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*

Observers: Liliana Chavarría - Duriaux, Georges Duriaux, Moisés Siles, Jessie and Cal Stuebner.

Hudsonian Godwit

Limosa haemastica

April 15, 2018. Location: Laguna de Tisma, Masaya.

First documented report with photo. An individual in breeding plumage feeding was observed and photographed.

Observer: Yoleidi Mejía

28 March, 2003. Location: Miskito Cays, Northern Caribbean. 40 individuals were reported by Jeffrey McCrary. This report was only validated in ebird until after the first documented report was recorded.

5 April, 2019. Location: Los Farallones, Estero Real, Department of Chinandega. 3 individuals were reported and photographed by Erica Reyes.

24 April, 2022. Location: Arrocera El Valle, Sébaco, Matagalpa. 2 individuals were reported and photographed by Danilo Moreno. Other observers: Ana Canales and Clan Thamnophilus Team.

So many records in different parts of the country indicate that the species is a passage migrant in March and April and, that it is more abundant than previously estimated.

The species, scarcely distributed, breeds in the boreal summer in Alaska and the extreme north of Canada. It spends the boreal winter in Argentina, Uruguay and southern Chile.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Black Turnstone *Arenaria melanocephala*

12 May, 2018. Location: Delta del Estero Real, Department of Chinandega.

An individual was sighted and photographed while feeding with a group of *Arenaria interpres*.

Probably the same individual was reported and photographed on 11 and 13 July at the same site by Salvadora Morales, Erika Reyes y José Martín Vallecillo.

This species breeds during the boreal summer on the east coast of Alaska and spends the boreal winter in the Pacific coastal areas from southern Alaska to Baja California in Mexico. It is therefore very rare in Nicaragua where it is probably a vagrant.

This species was not listed in the *Hypothetical Species* appendix of *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observers: Orlando Jarquín (photographer) and two other people from Quetzalli Nicaragua (their names are not mentioned in the report).

Ruff *Calidris pugnax*

October 17, 2022. Location: Arrocería del Valle, Sébaco, Matagalpa.

Two individuals were sighted and photographed on a flooded rice terrace in a mixed group with *Tringa flavipes*.

Eurasian species that breeds from the northeastern part of Europe and northern subarctic part of Russia, its wintering area is in western Europe and sub-Saharan Africa, coasts of India and southeast Asia. However, records in North America and the West Indies are numerous, decreasing in Central America and even fewer in South America. An Eurasian vagrant in Nicaragua is expected on both coasts.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observers: Danny Munguía (photographer), Erica Reyes, Michael Gutiérrez, Yoleidi Mejía and Danilo Moreno (photographer).

Bonaparte's Gull *Chroicocephalus philadelphia*

January 3, 2021. Location: Masachapa, Managua.

One individual with non-breeding plumage was photographed. The species was again reported and photographed at the same site on 6 February 2022.

Several reports in neighboring countries from Belize to Panama suggest that the species may be an accidental winter resident on both coasts.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observer and photographer: Danilo Moreno.

Audubon's Shearwater *Puffinus lherminieri*

May 6, 2019. Location: Corn Island pelagic area. Caribe Sur.

Two reports were made on the same day: the first at 8:18 in the east pelagic area of Corn Island and the second at 10:00 in the west area.

Pelagic migrant.

It breeds in the Bahamas, the West Indies, the islets east of Nicaragua (Providence Island) and the islands northwest of Panama. It is also known to be distributed in the pelagic waters of the Caribbean waters belonging to Nicaragua.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observers: first Amanda Guercio, second Geoff Carpentier.

Double-crested Cormorant *Nannopterum auritum*

25 December 2019. Location: Corn Island. Caribe Sur.

One individual was sighted and photographed. Part of its wintering range includes Florida, the Yucatan Peninsula and Cuba. There are reports of ebirds on the Islas de la Bahía, northern coast of Honduras, Jamaica, Haiti, Dominican Republic and Puerto Rico; this increases the possibility of encountering vagrants on Corn Island and Little Corn Island.

Observer and photographer: Manfred Bienert.

White-faced Ibis *Plegadis chihi*

January 29th, 2019. Location: Arrocera del Valle, Matagalpa.

One individual was sighted and photographed. This is the first documented record with photos in Nicaragua, and is the first report in the central part of the country; the observer has another record with photo on 16 February 2022 at the same site.

There are historical reports from March and November 2001, and 12 January, 2002 at El Guayabo, Granada, by Jørgen Peter Kjeldsen and a 9 September, 2016 record by Jeffrey McCrary at El Tránsito, León.

The southernmost wintering range of the species reaches the coasts of El Salvador, recent records in Honduras in the Gulf of Fonseca, a historical record in Costa Rica (1800), another from 2016 and records in eastern Panama suggest that the species is an accidental winter resident south of its normal range.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observer and photographer: Danilo Moreno.

Short-eared Owl *Asio flammeus*

26 January 2022. Location: Arrocera del Valle, Sébaco, Matagalpa.

One individual was sighted and photographed. Up to three individuals were reported by different observers between 22 January and 21 March. The species, is widely distributed in different continents. In the Americas they have their breeding grounds in Alaska (USA), Canada and northern United States, but also in the Greater Antilles (Cuba, Hispaniola and Puerto Rico) as well as in different countries of South America. Its wintering range is from southern Canada to the Gulf of Mexico and Florida, but also accidental in Guatemala and the Lesser Antilles. Therefore, the is species is probably an accidental winter resident in Nicaragua.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observer and photographer: Danilo Moreno.

Loggerhead Kingbird *Tyrannus caudifasciatus*

July 21st and 22nd, 2011. Location: Little Corn Island, Caribe Sur.

One individual was sighted over several days; the observer pointed out the differences with *Tyrannus tyrannus*, a similar species which is a passage migrant through the area between mid-March and mid-May. The Loggerhead Kingbird is a breeding resident in the Greater Antilles; in Nicaragua is a vagrant.

Observer: Carlo Castellani

Sinaloa Martin *Progne sinaloae*

March 21st, 2014. Location: Río Piedra Wetlands - San Miguelito, Caribe Sur.

One individual observed with excellent visibility conditions at 10 m distance. The species breeds in the Sierra Madre Occidental in northwestern Mexico, however, the distribution of the non-breeding season is unknown, although it is suspected that it spends its wintering season in northern South America. Records from ebird in southern Mexico, a specimen collected in Guatemala (1926), a report in the Gulf of Fonseca in Honduras (May 2018), another report in the Gulf of Nicoya in Costa Rica (October 2018), and this report in Nicaragua suggest a route to and from South America. Current vagrant status in our country could change to passage migrant. Species **VU**.

Observers: Elisabet Jané and Santiago Cuellar.

Northern Mockingbird *Mimus polyglottos*

22 March, 2018. Location: Hotel las Mercedes airport area, Managua.

One individual was sighted and duly distinguished from the similar species *Mimus gilvus*. Different reports of this species have been made in the Pacific area of Nicaragua, but they have been considered doubtful. On 8 October, 2022 Janeth García presents a new report in Jinotepe Carazo, with photographs that leave no doubt about the identification of the species.

Breeding range and wintering range are coincident, ranging from the southern Canada, the United States and Mexico to the Isthmus of Tehuantepec and the Greater Antilles. However, there are numerous reports of vagrants in Belize, Honduras, El Salvador, Nicaragua and Costa Rica.

Observer: John Thomton.

Rufous-backed Robin *Turdus rufopalliatus*

March 12, 2021. Location: Las Cruces, Nueva Segovia.

One individual was sighted and duly documented with photos and video (<https://ebird.org/checklist/S88599996>). The species is endemic to Mexico, common and widely distributed in central and western Mexico as far as the Isthmus of Tehuantepec.

The species was found in the appropriate habitat and altitude. This report from Nicaragua is the only one known from Central America, and although it is extremely rare to find it in Nicaragua, identification through documentation leaves no room for doubt. The species is considered vagrant in the country.

Observer and photographer: Manuel Aguilar.

Lark Sparrow *Chondestes grammacus*

January 12, 2021. Location: San Francisco Libre, Managua.

An individual observed and duly documented with photographs.

Although the wintering range extends from the southern United States to the Isthmus of Tehuantepec in Mexico, numerous records of vagrants have been documented in Belize, Guatemala, Honduras, El Salvador, Nicaragua and Costa Rica.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observer and photographer: Danilo Moreno.

Lincoln's Sparrow *Melospiza lincolnii*

April 4, 2020. Location: Miraflor, Estelí.

One individual was sighted, photographed and later identified. On 11 December of the same year another individual was photographed by Óscar Rodríguez Siles in the Reserva Natural Datanlí - el Diablo in Jinotega. The wintering distribution of the species extends in various parts of the United States, Mexico and, in Central America to south of Honduras almost reaching the border with Nicaragua, therefore, it was expected to be found in Nicaragua. There are also records of vagrant birds in Costa Rica.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observers: Danilo Moreno (photographer) and Francisco Muñoz.

Swainson's Warbler *Limnothlypis swainsonii*

22 March, 2017. Location: Andris Tara, Kipla Sait Tasbaika indigenous territory, Bosawas, Caribe Norte.

One individual was captured and photographed. The wintering distribution of the species includes the Greater Antilles and the Yucatan Peninsula (Belize and Guatemala). On 22 September, 2020 José Rojas makes another record of the species in northeast Siuna, Caribe Norte. The species can be expected as accidental winter resident.

Observer: Heydi Herrera (photographer) and Claudia Rebeca Benavente.

Orange-crowned Warbler *Leiothlypis celata*

14 March, 2020. Location: El Jaguar Reserve, Jinotega.

The wintering grounds of the species extend from the southern United States, Mexico and as far south as Guatemala and El Salvador. However, there are records of vagrants in Honduras, Costa Rica and Nicaragua where the species is an accidental winter resident.

Already described as expected in *Birds of Nicaragua*.

Observer: Nick Bayly.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To Dr. Jean Michel Maes, editor, for his valuable collaboration by reading countless times the drafts of this paper; to Dr. Eric van den Berghe for doing the same with the English version and editing it; and to Georges Duriaux for his contribution looking for possible errors in the data tables as in the manuscript.

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Lark Sparrow - *Chondestes grammacus* (Photo by Danilo Moreno).